

Quantum Evolution of the Universe

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Abstract: To address the unsolved problems of cosmology, we present a quantum model for the complete evolution of the universe based on laws of quantum mechanics and entanglement. According to our model, the universe is probabilistically exponentially accelerating in successive quantum epoch with decreasing probability. Like multi-particle entangled state, all galaxies and stars get entangled and the number of galaxies increasing exponentially in successive quantum epochs and they can actively and probabilistically survive forever due to entanglement. The model can correctly predict Hubble constant, energy and mass density of the universe, age of the universe, temperature of the universe, relative strength of fundamental forces and it can explain long-standing cosmological problems such as dark matter and dark energy, horizon problem, galactic structures, the observed asymmetry of matter and anti-matter and spinning motion of planets, star and galactic structures. This apart, the model can predict the orbital periods of planets and angular momentum of rotational motion of planets without using any gravitational theory or gravitational constant and showed how all observably stable elements can be produced through quantum nucleosynthesis.

In the *Rig Veda* [1], the evolution of the universe was philosophically discussed at the dawn of ancient civilization. However, as scientific theory, the Big Bang theory [2] and the Steady-State theory [3,4] were developed just a century ago. The two theories are classical theories of evolution based on general relativity. Later, quantum cosmology [5-12] has also been developed to deal with certain aspect of evolution. Big bang cosmology has been widely accepted model of evolution of the universe.

There are many unsolved long-standing problems of Big Bang cosmology. There is a undercurrent feelings that a radically new model or radical modification of big bang model needs to be developed to solve all these problems. Is it possible to develop quantum model for the entire evolution of the universe based on elementary quantum mechanics? There is no such model. As quantum information and entanglement have revealed new strength of quantum mechanics so the possibility cannot be ruled out by any laws of physics as long as space and time are not decoded. Keeping this possibility in mind with an open mind we develop a simple entanglement-based quantum model for the evolution of the universe. We first present the axioms of the model. We then elaborate on these axioms and show that the model can explain vast cosmological, astrophysical, and nuclear data, which so far cannot be explained.

1. At $t = 0$, a quantum of quanta of space, called *qtom*, and a quantum of quanta of time, called *qtim*, are created. The moment of creation of the first *qtom*-*qtim* pair may be called the 0th quantum epoch (*qepoch*). The moment of creation may also be called *quantum quiet*.

2. A *qtom* can contain only one neutron-antineutron pair. With the simultaneous creation of a *qtom* and a *qtim*, an entangled pair of virtual neutron and anti-neutron ($n\bar{n}$) is created with either anti-parallel or parallel spin, each with a probability of 1/2. The spin state of the entangled neutron and anti-neutron may be expressed as,

$$|\psi_n\bar{\psi}_n\rangle_1 = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(|\uparrow_n\rangle|\downarrow_{\bar{n}}\rangle + |\downarrow_n\rangle|\uparrow_{\bar{n}}\rangle).$$

$$|\psi_n\bar{\psi}_n\rangle_2 = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(|\uparrow_n\rangle|\uparrow_{\bar{n}}\rangle + |\downarrow_n\rangle|\downarrow_{\bar{n}}\rangle).$$

where $|\uparrow_n\rangle$ and $|\downarrow_n\rangle$ are the spin states of neutron and $|\uparrow_{\bar{n}}\rangle$ and $|\downarrow_{\bar{n}}\rangle$ are the spin states of anti-neutron.

3. If $|\psi_n\bar{\psi}_n\rangle_1$ is created in the first *qtom*, then the virtual entangled $n\bar{n}$ pair will experience attractive quantum spin force arising from the anti-parallel spin of n and \bar{n} . After that the virtual pair is annihilated within the first *qtim*.

4. If $|\psi_n\bar{\psi}_n\rangle_2$ is created, the virtual entangled $n\bar{n}$ pair will experience a repulsive QS force arising from the parallel spin of n and \bar{n} . For the manifestation of the repulsive QS force, there is no extra space in the *qtom* and no extra *qtim*. To manifest the force, and by the action of the force, a new *qtom* is created. With the creation of *qtom*-*qtim*, the virtual pair is annihilated. The time period between the creation of the first and second *qtom* may be called the 1st *qepoch*.

5. At the end of the 1st *qepoch*, there are two parent *qtoms*. After the creation of a new *qtim*, a virtual $n\bar{n}$ pair with parallel or anti-parallel spin is created with probability 1/2 in either of the two *qtoms*. If $|\psi_n\bar{\psi}_n\rangle_2$ is created, a new *qtom* will be formed by the action of the repulsive QS force. Similarly, another *qtom* will be created from the second *qtom*. In a *qtim*, one *qtom* will be created with probability 1/2. The time period between the creation of the second and fourth *qtom* may be called the 2nd *qepoch*.

6. At the end of the 2nd *qepoch*, there are four parent *qtoms*. With the creation of *qtims* along with *qtoms*, four daughter *qtoms* are generated from the four parent *qtoms*, each with a probability of 1/4. This process of probabilistic creation of *qtoms* and *qtims* is continued

7. *Qtoms* are not created in one dimension only. *Qtoms* are created in three dimensions simultaneously, on average, in each *qtim*. At the end of r -th *qepoch*, the number of *qtoms* along three dimension will be 2^r . As in each *qtim* $|\psi_n\bar{\psi}_n\rangle_2$ is generated with probability 1/2, the total number of *qtims* is $\sim 2^{r/3+1}$. A *qepoch* is a time period which all parent *qtoms* generate daughter *qtoms*.

8. Quantum of quanta creates the structure of space and time, which is discrete within a discrete structure. Here, discreteness at the Planck length is nested within discreteness at the nuclear scale. The discreteness of space and time is hierarchical and created probabilistically.

9. Maximum speed of expansion of space may be defined as the speed of creation of space, $C = \Delta x / \Delta t$, where Δx is the dimension of a qtom and Δt is the dimension of a qtim. $|\psi_n \bar{\psi}_n\rangle_1$ and $|\psi_n \bar{\psi}_n\rangle_2$ are created with probability 1/2, and a qtom is created only when $|\psi_n \bar{\psi}_n\rangle_2$ is created. This ensures the probabilistic expansion of space. This also ensure the maximum speed of expansion of space.

10. The probability of creation of a qtom, P_q , is inversely proportional to the total number of parent qtoms. In r -th qepoch, in each qtim, a qtom is created with probability $P_q \sim 1/2^r$. The probabilities of creation of qtom in x , y and z -direction within a qtim will be same: $P_x = P_y = P_z = \sqrt[3]{P_q}$.

11. The entire length, D , of the universe will always expand with speed $\sim C/2$ since in each qtim a qtom will be generated with a probability of 1/2 over the entire dimension. The length of space per cosmological unit will always expand with a speed less than $C/2$ since in each qtim, on average, less than a qtom will be generated over a length less than D .

12. In a qepoch, the probability P_x increases with the decrease in the number of remaining parent qtoms. Otherwise, the speed of expansion will arbitrarily exceed C . In the r -th qepoch, a daughter qtom generated in the r -th qepoch will not generate a new qtom along with the parent qtom in the same qepoch. During the previous qepoch, parent qtoms wait to generate qtoms, so a parent qtom has a greater probability of generating a qtom than a daughter qtom. A daughter qtom will become a parent qtom in the next qepoch. If daughter qtoms generate qtoms along with parent qtoms with the same probability, the speed of expansion will arbitrarily exceed C .

13. In the beginning of r -th qepoch, $P_x = \frac{1}{2^r}$. At the end of r -th qepoch, $P_x = \frac{1}{2^{r-1}}$. In the beginning of $r+1$ -th qepoch, $P_x = \frac{1}{2^{r+1}}$. At the end of $r+1$ -th qepoch, $P_x = \frac{1}{2^r}$. Space less than D will decelerate in successive qepochs since P_x decreases in successive qepochs. However, space less than D will accelerate during a qepoch since P_x increases during a qepoch. In different qepochs, the acceleration will be non-uniform.

14. A virtual pair can survive with some probability $P_{n\bar{n}}$. That is, an $n\bar{n}$ pair can be permanently separated due to the repulsive QS force created with probability, $P_{n\bar{n}}$, which is also the probability of permanent violation of the principle of conservation of angular momentum along any of the three dimension. Therefore, the probability, $P_{n\bar{n}}$, will be equal to the probability of generation of a qtom in one dimension: $P_{n\bar{n}} = \sqrt[3]{P_q} = \frac{1}{2^r}$

15. In r -th qepoch, the number of qtoms generating real $n-\bar{n}$ pair is 2^r . In r -th qepoch, the expected number of generated real $n-\bar{n}$ pairs is,

$$N_n \approx P_{n\bar{n}} \cdot 2^r \approx 2^{2r/3}.$$

16. The generated $n-\bar{n}$ pair will carry quantum energy E_q , used to confine the pair in qtom. With the creation of a real $n-\bar{n}$ pair, the principles of conservation of energy and spin angular momentum will be permanently violated with probability $P_{n\bar{n}}$.

17. During a qtim, three fundamental quantum forces – the quantum spin (QS) force, the quantum charge (QC) force and the quantum mass (QM) force are activated due to spin, charge and mass, respectively, with probabilities P_s , P_c and P_m , respectively, where $P_s + P_c + P_m = 1$. These quantum forces are not continuously active; instead they are activated probabilistically.

18. All three fundamental quantum forces are attractive and repulsive in nature. Particles and antiparticles experience a repulsive QM force. Mass, charge, and spin are not the measures of the three fundamental quantum forces; rather, the number of particles/antiparticles associated with mass, charge, and spin is the measure of the probabilistic scores of the forces.

19. Quantum forces act only between entangled states. Two masses, two charges, and two particles with spins will experience QM force, QC force, and QS force, respectively, if they are directly or indirectly entangled. Three fundamental quantum forces are manifested due to entanglement. These three fundamental forces are of $1/R^2$ nature, since the probability of two particles being entangled is $1/R^2$, where R is the distance between the two entangled particles

20. These three fundamental quantum forces are independent and cannot be further unified. Gravity is already quantum. The strong nuclear force, weak nuclear force, magnetic force, and electromagnetic force are different manifestations of QS and QC forces. The universe and its galactic structures and substructures will evolve under the action of these three fundamental forces.

21. Neutrons and antineutrons will drift away from each other due to repulsive QS and repulsive QM forces. An entangled $n-\bar{n}$ pair emerges from qtom with quantum energy E_q and spin angular momentum. Quantum energy E_q is the ultimate source of all energy in the universe, and spin angular momentum is the source of angular momentum of all bodies in the universe. Entanglement will play a crucial role in the sharing of quantum energy and angular momentum among particles and antiparticles.

22. Neutron is a composite particle of a proton and an electron ($n = p + e$). The spin of its proton and electron periodically flips. The proton and electron of the neutron will experience an attractive QS force as long as their spins are anti-parallel, and during this time the neutron remains stable. The proton and electron of the neutron will experience a repulsive QS force if their spins become parallel, and then the

neutron will be unstable. The same is true for the entangled anti-neutron, which is a composite particle of an antiproton and a positron ($\bar{n} = \bar{p} + \bar{e}$).

23. In an entangled neutron–antineutron pair, when the neutron decays ($n \rightarrow p + e$), the antineutron remains stable, and when the antineutron decays ($\bar{n} \rightarrow \bar{p} + \bar{e}$), the neutron remains stable. The generated protons and electrons remain entangled with the stable antineutron. Similarly, the generated antiproton and positron remain entangled with the stable neutron. In these entangled transformations, conservation of spin angular momentum is violated separately but not jointly by particles and antiparticles. The entangled energy of the pair will be shared among the proton, electron, stable antineutron, positron, antiproton, and neutron.

24. The entangled state, $|\psi_n \bar{\psi}_n\rangle_1$, can evolve in the two ways:

$$\begin{aligned} |\psi_n \bar{\psi}_n\rangle_{21} &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (|\uparrow_n \rangle |\uparrow_{\bar{n}} \rangle + |\downarrow_n \rangle |\downarrow_{\bar{n}} \rangle) \\ &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (|\uparrow_p \downarrow_e \rangle + |\uparrow_{\bar{p}} \uparrow_{\bar{e}} \rangle + |\downarrow_p \uparrow_e \rangle + |\downarrow_{\bar{p}} \downarrow_{\bar{e}} \rangle) \\ &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (|n \rangle |\uparrow_{\bar{p}} \uparrow_{\bar{e}} \rangle + |n \rangle |\downarrow_{\bar{p}} \downarrow_{\bar{e}} \rangle) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} |\psi_n \bar{\psi}_n\rangle_{22} &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (|\uparrow_n \rangle |\uparrow_{\bar{n}} \rangle + |\downarrow_n \rangle |\downarrow_{\bar{n}} \rangle) \\ &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (|\uparrow_p \uparrow_e \rangle + |\uparrow_{\bar{p}} \downarrow_{\bar{e}} \rangle + |\downarrow_p \downarrow_e \rangle + |\downarrow_{\bar{p}} \uparrow_{\bar{e}} \rangle) \\ &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (|\uparrow_p \uparrow_e \rangle |\bar{n} \rangle + |\downarrow_p \downarrow_e \rangle |\bar{n} \rangle) \end{aligned}$$

25. In $|\psi_n \bar{\psi}_n\rangle_{21}$, neutron remains stable as it experiences attractive QS force, whereas the entangled electron and proton experience a repulsive QS force. Similarly, in $|\psi_n \bar{\psi}_n\rangle_{22}$ the anti-neutron remains stable as it experiences an attractive QS force, whereas the entangled positron and anti-proton experience a repulsive QS force. The neutron and anti-neutron can be either stable or unstable with a probability of 1/2. The stable state of the composite neutron/antineutron may be considered a spin-0 state. In these entangled transformations, the principle of conservation of angular momentum is not violated.

26. Entangled protons and electrons will experience a repulsive QS force, an attractive QC force, and an attractive QM force. Entangled proton–electron pairs and stable antineutrons will also experience a repulsive QM force. Stable neutrons and antiproton–positron pairs will also experience a repulsive QM force. Under the combined effect of repulsive and attractive quantum forces, protons, electrons, and neutrons will accumulate. The same is true for antiparticles. Particles and antiparticles will use their common quantum energy E_q to experience quantum forces for accumulation.

27. In matter and anti-matter cloud, quantum nucleosynthesis begins with the synchronous creation of entangled deuteron and anti-deuteron (${}^1_2D \leftrightarrow {}^1_2\bar{D}$). A deuteron 1_2D is formed through the fusion of a

proton and a stable neutron while an anti-deuteron $\frac{1}{2}\bar{D}$ is produced through the fusion of an anti-proton and a stable anti-neutron. The entangled $\frac{1}{2}D \leftrightarrow \frac{1}{2}\bar{D}$ pair is formed due to the action of attractive QS force.

28. In entangled $\frac{1}{2}D \leftrightarrow \frac{1}{2}\bar{D}$ pair, either a proton is entangled with a stable anti-neutron or a stable neutron is entangled with an anti-proton. The entangled $\frac{1}{2}D \leftrightarrow \frac{1}{2}\bar{D}$ pair remains stable as a system of entangled singlet states, in which the spins undergo periodic flipping. Conservation of spin angular momentum is individually violated in the deuteron and anti-deuteron but it is jointly –and periodically – conserved in $\frac{1}{2}D \leftrightarrow \frac{1}{2}\bar{D}$ system.

29. During quantum nucleo-synthesis, many $\frac{1}{2}D \leftrightarrow \frac{1}{2}\bar{D}$ pairs become entangled, forming a web of $\frac{1}{2}D \leftrightarrow \frac{1}{2}\bar{D}$. The number of such entangled entities in the web increases linearly. Each $\frac{1}{2}D \leftrightarrow \frac{1}{2}\bar{D}$ pair can remain entangled with a free stable neutron and anti-neutron. These free stable neutrons and anti-neutrons play a crucial role in the formation of progressively higher entangled matter and anti-matter nuclei.

30. Quantum energy available in the neutron and proton provides the required binding energy for the formation of $\frac{1}{2}D \leftrightarrow \frac{1}{2}\bar{D}$. The total quantum energy increases linearly with the entanglement of many $\frac{1}{2}D \leftrightarrow \frac{1}{2}\bar{D}$ pairs, with decreasing probability. With the creation many of $\frac{1}{2}D \leftrightarrow \frac{1}{2}\bar{D}$ pairs, multi-particle/anti-particle entanglement is established. Due to multi-particle/anti-particle entanglement, quantum energy is shared among all entangled entities.

31. Entangled helium and anti-helium, ${}^2_4\text{He} \leftrightarrow {}^2_4\bar{\text{He}}$ are synchronously created through the fusion of an entangled pair of deuteron and anti-deuteron with another unentangled pair of deuteron and anti-deuteron wherein angular momentum is jointly and periodically conserved. The entangled ${}^2_4\text{He} \leftrightarrow {}^2_4\bar{\text{He}}$ is formed through the action of attractive QS force. The quantum energy, E_q is released as binding energy during the formation of ${}^2_4\text{He} \leftrightarrow {}^2_4\bar{\text{He}}$.

32. The following two different entangled states of helium and antihelium, ${}^2_4\text{He} \leftrightarrow {}^2_4\bar{\text{He}}$, can form from two entangled deuteron and anti-deuteron states, $|\psi_{\frac{1}{2}D}\bar{\psi}_{\frac{1}{2}D}\rangle_1$ and $|\psi_{\frac{1}{2}D}\bar{\psi}_{\frac{1}{2}D}\rangle_2$:

$$|\psi_{{}^2_4\text{He}}\bar{\psi}_{{}^2_4\text{He}}\rangle_1 = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (|\psi_{\frac{1}{2}D}\bar{\psi}_{\frac{1}{2}D}\rangle_1|\psi_{\frac{1}{2}D}\bar{\psi}_{\frac{1}{2}D}\rangle_2 + |\psi_{\frac{1}{2}D}\bar{\psi}_{\frac{1}{2}D}\rangle_2|\psi_{\frac{1}{2}D}\bar{\psi}_{\frac{1}{2}D}\rangle_1)$$

$$|\psi_{{}^2_4\text{He}}\bar{\psi}_{{}^2_4\text{He}}\rangle_2 = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (|\psi_{\frac{1}{2}D}\bar{\psi}_{\frac{1}{2}D}\rangle_1|\psi_{\frac{1}{2}D}\bar{\psi}_{\frac{1}{2}D}\rangle_1 + |\psi_{\frac{1}{2}D}\bar{\psi}_{\frac{1}{2}D}\rangle_2|\psi_{\frac{1}{2}D}\bar{\psi}_{\frac{1}{2}D}\rangle_2)$$

33. Stable entangled nuclei Z and anti-nucleus \bar{Z} are synchronously produced by complete fusion reaction : $X + Y \rightarrow Z \leftrightarrow \bar{Z} \leftarrow \bar{X} + \bar{Y}$, where X and Y are stable nuclei, and \bar{X} and \bar{Y} are stable anti-nuclei. Entanglement provides stability to all non-radioactive nuclei and anti-nuclei. The $Z \leftrightarrow \bar{Z}$ state is synchronously formed by the action of the attractive QS force, in which angular momentum is both

jointly and periodically conserved. The available quantum energy E_q supplies the required binding energy for the formation of $Z \leftrightarrow \bar{Z}$.

34. Stable nucleus can also be asynchronously produced by fusion reaction : $X+Y \rightarrow Z+W$ or by beta decay after the synchronous production. Asynchronously produced nucleus W and Z become entangled with synchronously produced anti-nucleus \bar{W} and \bar{Z} , respectively, due to the quantum indistinguishability principle, and they will not jointly violate angular momentum conservation principles. Same is true for stable anti-nucleus.

35. Some entangled nuclei/anti-nuclei $Z \leftrightarrow \bar{Z}$ are produced through electron/positron capture, $X + e = Z \leftrightarrow \bar{Z} = \bar{X} + \bar{e}$, and some through positron/electron emission, $X + \bar{e} = Z \leftrightarrow \bar{Z} = \bar{X} + e$, where X and \bar{X} are synchronously produced by complete fusion reaction. The production of neutron/anti-neutron enriched $Z \leftrightarrow \bar{Z}$ is possible through all these three processes.

36. A partially stable nucleus is also produced due to entanglement. An unstable nucleus can be considered a direct product state of entangled and unentangled states. Entanglement provides partial stability to the radioactive nucleus/antinucleus.

37. Entangled atoms and anti-atoms are synchronously formed when an electron and a positron get entangled with an entangled nucleus and anti-nucleus. Like a nucleus, a single atom is asynchronously formed after the synchronous creation of an entangled atom and anti-atom. Entangled molecules and anti-molecules are synchronously formed when an electron and a positron get entangled with an entangled atom and anti-atom. Like a nucleus and an atom, a single molecule is asynchronously formed after the synchronous creation of an entangled molecule and anti-molecule.

38. Entangled nuclei, anti-nuclei, atoms, anti-atoms, molecules, and anti-molecules can form entangled web. Nucleus, atom and molecules are all quantum states.

39. Due to multi-particle entanglement, quantum energy E_q increases, which provides the necessary energy for fusion. Quantum nucleo-synthesis is possible in a star in the absence of a quantum tunneling effect. Quantum energy is the actual source of a star's energy. In a star, a fraction of quantum energy E_q is converted into radiation.

40. Initially, a stable neutron would not be able to accumulate with a proton and electron because the neutron has to provide the required energy to the anti-proton and positron to experience a repulsive QS force. In addition to this, a stable neutron is not entangled with a proton and an electron, so it cannot experience any attractive QM force for accumulation. Some percentage of stable neutrons will get entangled with protons during the formation of deuterons and anti-deuterons and contribute to the luminous mass. The same is true for a stable anti-neutron.

- 41. The remaining percentage of stable neutrons/antineutrons will not contribute to luminous mass and will remain invisible. The observed ratio of neutrons to protons in the universe will be less than 1.*
- 42. Like spin angular momentum, quantum energy E_q is an entangled quantity. Quantum energy is shared among entangled particles and anti-particles. Like the angular momentum energy conservation principle, it is separately violated with a probability of 1 in the matter universe and the anti-matter part of the universe, but it is jointly conserved in the entire universe. In a nuclear reaction, mass is not converted to energy and vice versa.*
- 43. Accumulated matter such as stars, planets, moons, etc. can produce all stable nuclei. However, the probability of producing nuclei increases with the density of matter or antimatter. The same is true for accumulated antimatter.*
- 44. The Sun and the planet will share entangled protons and electrons with a probability of $1/R^2$. A percentage of the shared entangled protons and electrons will have spins in the same direction. The Sun and the planet will experience a repulsive QS force due to this spin distribution*
- 45. The Sun and planets will experience attractive QM force and repulsive QS force. The orbital motion of planets is jointly initiated by two quantum forces and later continued by the attractive QM force. The rotational motion of planets is generated by the action of the repulsive QS force and the attractive QM force. Without using the laws of gravity, the orbital periods of planets can be predicted. Revolution and rotation are quantum phenomena.*
- 46. The Sun and planets may not be perfectly spherical, and the distribution of entangled protons and electrons in a star and its planets may also not be spherical. In the case of a non-spherical distribution, the orbit of a planet will not be perfectly circular .*
- 47. Entangled neutrons and anti-neutrons are produced with spin angular momentum. Later, entangled electron-proton pairs and positron-anti-proton pairs are produced, also with spin angular momentum. This spin angular momentum of particles and anti-particles is transferred to matter and anti-matter galaxies, stars, planets, and moons to generate angular momentum for revolution/rotation.*
- 48. Due to the presence of attractive QM force and repulsive QS force, matter and antimatter planets, moons, comets, and asteroids can form independently from the accumulated gas. All elements and anti-elements are produced in them, since a star's temperature is not required to produce elements and anti-elements.*
- 49. After the formation of many stars, planets, comets, asteroids, and moons, galaxies are formed. A pair of matter and anti-matter galaxies is the smallest entangled galactic structure. At the galactic center, a massive core can form due to the accumulation of particles. Stars experience attractive QM force and repulsive QS forces due to entanglement. Stars revolve around the galactic center due to the*

attractive QM force. Stars rotate around their axes under the action of attractive QM force and repulsive QS force.

50. Many matter galaxies will group together and form a galactic structure due to the influence of attractive QM force. Similarly, many galactic structures will form a higher galactic structure. Thus, higher and higher galactic structures will form with the increase in the number of galaxies in successive epochs. Similarly, higher and higher antimatter galactic structures will form. Galactic structures are hierarchical in nature.

51. Galactic structures and their substructures may revolve around their common barycenter. Galactic substructures can also rotate about their own axis due to a repulsive QS force and an attractive QM force. The spin angular momentum of entangled protons and electrons will provide the necessary angular momentum for both orbital and spinning motion and rotation.

52. Only the largest galactic structures of matter will be adjacent to the largest galactic structures of antimatter. Within the largest structures, the smaller structures will belong. The size and number of the largest structures will increase arbitrarily.

53. The entropy of the matter and antimatter distribution of galaxies increases exponentially in successive epochs, but the rate of entropy increment will decrease exponentially in successive epochs. The Shannon entropy of the distribution of galaxies in galactic structures is significantly less than a random distribution without any structure. The ratio of the Shannon entropy of the distribution of higher galactic structures to the smallest galactic structure will decrease with the increase of more and more higher structures.

54. Quantum Mechanics does not allow the eventual non-existence of all matter and antimatter galaxies/stars even in the arbitrarily distant future since it does not allow the destruction of all nuclei/anti-nuclei, atoms/anti-atoms, and molecules/anti-molecules, which are quantum states.

55. Newly evolving galaxies can share entangled particles and antiparticles with old galaxies. Stars in old galaxies can receive quantum energy from new galaxies due to entanglement.

56. In matter and antimatter stars, cyclic nuclear reactions take place due to a steady supply of the required energy by newly evolving galaxies through an entanglement channel. As a result, a star can generate continuous energy. Apart from statistical fluctuation, the energy output of a star/anti-star remains the same since the rate of energy generation and the rate of energy loss remain the same. Stars are not bound to die.

57. Due to statistical fluctuations of all the stability parameters, a star can become unstable with decreasing probability. The probability of a star becoming different unstable states, like a supernova, a red giant, or a white dwarf, will decrease with the increase in the number of stars in successive epochs.

58. Through quantum nucleosynthesis, elements were produced in planets, moons, and asteroids with some energy. However, the temperatures of hot planets, moons, and asteroids were much, much less than the temperature of an active main-sequence star. Hot planets, moons, and asteroids needed much more energy than the main-sequence stars to continue the cyclic nuclear reaction. But eventually, they cooled down since a newly evolving galaxy could not provide the required energy through an entanglement channel.

59.. As the mass of a star/galaxy is not the source of its energy output, luminosity is not a measure of its mass. The ratio of particle–antiparticle density to energy density will remain the same throughout the evolution of the universe.

60. In an epoch, particles and anti-particles will also undergo collision and generate radiation, losing some quantum energy. In successive epochs, quantum energy density decreases exponentially. With the expansion of the universe, the radiation density of the previous epochs also decreases exponentially in successive epochs. The universe will have a background temperature which will exponentially decrease with the exponential decrease of the particle density and quantum energy density in successive epochs.

61. Magnetic force, electromagnetic force, weak nuclear force, and strong nuclear force are different manifestations of quantum spin force.

62.. Due to the sharing of quantum energy, the energy of a particle can increase if it repeatedly experiences quantum forces with an increasing number of entangled particles and anti-particles in the entangled web. If a stable particle (n , p , e) acquires more and more energy, then energy can be dissipated with the creation of an unstable particle from the stable one. The number of different unstable particles will increase with the increase of energy of stable particles. The same is true for anti-particles.

63.. Speed of expansion of the entire dimension of the universe is $C/2$, since in each q_{tim} a q_{tom} in one dimension is created with probability $1/2$. Unlike space, particle in one direction, so optimal speed of particle $c = C/2$. Constancy of the speed of light in vacuum arises from the optimal speed of expansion of space.

64. In and around a mass, q_{toms} are temporarily occupied by particles or anti-particles. As a result, the probability of the creation of a q_{tom} in and around a mass will be less than in a vacuum. To conserve the probability, the probability away from a mass will increase. As a result, space can distort. Not the mass itself, but the presence of mass can be the cause of the distortion of space.

65. Space will have some sort of ripples or distortion due to statistical fluctuation in the generation of q_{toms} in each point in space. This unevenness of space will affect all measurements and generate noise.

The fractional error due to this space noise can, on the average, be reduced if statistics of measurement is increased. Space noise is the fundamental source of statistical noise.

66. *Since space and time are created probabilistically, they cannot be controlled by any means.*

67. *Due to entanglement, quantum forces act instantaneously. A message can be transmitted instantaneously by exploiting quantum forces, without violating the principle of causality.*

68. *Information of random generation of qtom cannot be lost due to unitarity. It can be recovered to generate random numbers. The universe itself is the biggest random number generator of the universe.*

69. *Due to the probabilistic expansion of the universe, position-information cannot be precisely known, even if complete information of momentum is known, and vice versa. There is an uncertainty on top of the uncertainty principle of quantum mechanics.*

70. *The universe is quantum mechanically created so that the human species evolves with consciousness to decode the quantum evolution of the universe, to verify quantum mechanics, and to preserve and protect information and other species.*

Now we shall discuss the axioms in detail and examine how the model can interpret the vast amount of observational data.

1. Speed of expansion of the universe : The speed of expansion of the universe may be defined as the length of space generated per unit time per unit cosmological distance. So the speed is the product of the number of qtoms generated per unit time and per unit cosmological distance and the dimension of qtom : $V = M \cdot \nabla x$ where M is number of qtoms generated per unit time and per unit cosmological space. In a qepoch, P_x is the probability of creation of a qtom along the x axis during an epoch. N_t is the number of qtoms per unit time, N_x is the number of qtoms per unit length of space. So, $M \sim P_x \cdot N_t \cdot N_x$ and $V \sim P_x \cdot N_t \cdot N_x \cdot \nabla x$. According to our model, the optimal speed of expansion of the universe will be C when entire dimension of the universe is considered.

$$P_x \sim \frac{C}{N_t \cdot N_x \cdot \nabla x} \sim \frac{C}{N_t \cdot D}$$

$D = N_x \cdot \nabla x$ where D is the dimension of the universe. Let us assume that dimension of the observable universe is the dimension of the universe. The dimension of the observable universe is $D \approx 28$ gigapersec. According to our model, the optimal speed of a particle is on the order of optimal speed of the universe, so $C \approx 10^{10}$ cm/sec/D. $\nabla x \approx 10^{-13}$ cm; $N_x \approx 10^{39}/D$; $\nabla t \approx 10^{-24}$ sec; $N_t \approx 10^{24}/\text{sec}$. $C_q = \Delta x/\Delta t \approx 10^{10}$ cm/sec. Putting the value, we get $P_x \approx 10^{-40}$. So $P_q = P_x^3 \approx 10^{-120}$. The total number of total number of qtoms in the universe is $N \approx 10^{120} \approx 2^{400}$. The universe is currently passing through ~ 400 -th qepoch. Putting the value of P_x we get $V \approx 10^6$ cm/sec/Mpc. This is close to Hubble constant [16], which is the speed of expansion of space per Mpc. So, $H \sim P_x \cdot N_t \cdot N_x \cdot \nabla x$. Hubble constant will exponentially decrease in the coming qepochs.

2. Acceleration of the universe: In a qepoch, P_x increases with time since number of parent qtoms decreases with time. As a result, speed of expansion of space of length $L < D$ will increase with time. Speed of expansion of L at the end of an qepoch will be twice of the speed of expansion of L at the end of an qepoch. So in an epoch length of space less than the maximum dimension will accelerate.

According to the model, the time period, of a qepoch increases exponentially. It suggests that the time period of the present qepoch cannot be 4 billion years; it must be 8 billion years, since age of the universe is $T_u \sim 13.8$ billion years ($T_u \sim \dots + 0.12 + 0.25 + 0.5 + 1 + 2 + 4 + 8 \dots \approx 13.8$ billion years). Therefore, according to our model, the current qepoch began approximately $13.8 - 8 \approx 6$ billion years ago. Thus, space on a cosmological scale began to accelerate about 6 billion years ago. Since $\nabla v \approx 10^6$ $cm/sec/Mpc$, the acceleration is $a = \frac{\nabla v}{\nabla t} \approx 10^{-11}$ $cm^2/sec/Mpc$. The acceleration per unit cosmological length of space will decrease exponentially in successive qepochs. Hence, the model can explain the observed acceleration [17,18] of the universe, which corresponds to the acceleration of the universe in the current qepoch. However, in successive qepochs, the average speed of expansion of L will decrease exponentially. This deceleration can be observed after 2 to 3 billion years, when the current qepoch will end.

3. Age of the universe : At present qepoch, the number of qtoms is $N \approx 10^{120}$, and the number of qtims is $N_t \approx 10^{40}$. The time period of the present qepoch of the universe is given by the product of the present number of qtims and the time each qtim represents. Thus the age of the universe can be expressed as $T_{age} = N_t \cdot \nabla t \approx 10^{40} \cdot 10^{-24} Sec. \approx 10$ billion years. This is consistent with the measured age of the universe.

4. Quantum Nucleosynthesis : Quantum Nucleosynthesis begins with the creation of the following two entangled states

$$|\psi_n \bar{\psi}_n\rangle_{21} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (|\uparrow_p \downarrow_e\rangle + |\uparrow_{\bar{p}} \uparrow_{\bar{e}}\rangle + |\downarrow_p \uparrow_e\rangle + |\downarrow_{\bar{p}} \downarrow_{\bar{e}}\rangle)$$

$$|\psi_n \bar{\psi}_n\rangle_{22} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (|\uparrow_p \uparrow_e\rangle + |\uparrow_{\bar{p}} \downarrow_{\bar{e}}\rangle + |\downarrow_p \downarrow_e\rangle + |\downarrow_{\bar{p}} \uparrow_{\bar{e}}\rangle)$$

Deuteron is the building block of all elements. In the accumulated mass, a stable neutron can hit a proton and vice versa. If the spin of the electron of the stable neutron and the free proton are anti-parallel, then the free proton will capture the electron and form a new neutron. If the spin direction of the new neutron and the remaining proton are opposite, they will experience an attractive QS force and will form the spin-0 state of deuteron $\frac{1}{2}D$ (however, the deuteron spin is assigned to be 1). If the spins of the electron of the stable neutron and the free proton are parallel, the electron will not be captured by the free proton.

Similarly, a free anti-proton and stable anti-neutron can form spin-0 state of $\frac{1}{2}\bar{D}$. If spin of the positron and the other \bar{p} are opposite, then the free \bar{p} will capture the positron and form a new \bar{n} . If the spin of the new anti-neutron and the remaining anti-proton are opposite, they will experience an

attractive QS force and will form the spin-0 state of anti-deuteron $\frac{1}{2}\bar{D}$. Deuteron $\frac{1}{2}D$ and anti-deuteron $\frac{1}{2}\bar{D}$ can form in the following probable ways.

$$\begin{aligned}
|n\rangle|\downarrow_p\rangle &\rightarrow |\downarrow_p\uparrow_e\rangle|\downarrow_p\rangle \rightarrow |\downarrow_p\rangle|\uparrow_e\downarrow_p\rangle \rightarrow |\downarrow_p\rangle|\uparrow_n\rangle \rightarrow |\psi_{\frac{1}{2}D}\rangle_1 \\
|\bar{n}\rangle|\downarrow_{\bar{p}}\rangle &\rightarrow |\downarrow_{\bar{p}}\uparrow_{\bar{e}}\rangle|\downarrow_{\bar{p}}\rangle \rightarrow |\downarrow_{\bar{p}}\rangle|\uparrow_{\bar{e}}\downarrow_{\bar{p}}\rangle \rightarrow |\downarrow_{\bar{p}}\rangle|\uparrow_{\bar{n}}\rangle \rightarrow |\bar{\psi}_{\frac{1}{2}D}\rangle_1 \\
|n\rangle|\uparrow_p\rangle &\rightarrow |\uparrow_p\downarrow_e\rangle|\uparrow_p\rangle \rightarrow |\uparrow_p\rangle|\downarrow_e\uparrow_p\rangle \rightarrow |\uparrow_p\rangle|\downarrow_n\rangle \rightarrow |\psi_{\frac{1}{2}D}\rangle_2 \\
|\bar{n}\rangle|\uparrow_{\bar{p}}\rangle &\rightarrow |\uparrow_{\bar{p}}\downarrow_{\bar{e}}\rangle|\uparrow_{\bar{p}}\rangle \rightarrow |\uparrow_{\bar{p}}\rangle|\downarrow_{\bar{e}}\uparrow_{\bar{p}}\rangle \rightarrow |\uparrow_{\bar{p}}\rangle|\downarrow_{\bar{n}}\rangle \rightarrow |\bar{\psi}_{\frac{1}{2}D}\rangle_2
\end{aligned}$$

Deuteron and anti-deuteron produced in this way can become entangled if either \bar{n} p pair is entangled or the $n\bar{p}$ pair is entangled. In that case, an entangled pair of a deuteron and an anti-deuteron can form synchronously by sharing a common quantum energy through the entanglement channel. The following two singlet states of $\frac{1}{2}\bar{D}$ and anti-deuteron $\frac{1}{2}\bar{D}$ can then arise.

$$\begin{aligned}
|\psi_{\frac{1}{2}D}\bar{\psi}_{\frac{1}{2}D}\rangle_1 &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(|\psi_{\frac{1}{2}D}\rangle_1 |\bar{\psi}_{\frac{1}{2}D}\rangle_2 + |\psi_{\frac{1}{2}D}\rangle_2 |\bar{\psi}_{\frac{1}{2}D}\rangle_1) \\
|\psi_{\frac{1}{2}D}\bar{\psi}_{\frac{1}{2}D}\rangle_2 &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(|\psi_{\frac{1}{2}D}\rangle_1 |\bar{\psi}_{\frac{1}{2}D}\rangle_1 + |\psi_{\frac{1}{2}D}\rangle_2 |\bar{\psi}_{\frac{1}{2}D}\rangle_2)
\end{aligned}$$

According to our model, the spins of electron-proton and positron-anti-proton will periodically flip: $|\uparrow_n\rangle \rightarrow |\downarrow_p\uparrow_e\rangle$, $|\uparrow_n\rangle \rightarrow |\uparrow_p\downarrow_e\rangle$, $|\uparrow_n\rangle \rightarrow |\uparrow_p\uparrow_e\rangle$, $|\downarrow_n\rangle \rightarrow |\downarrow_p\downarrow_e\rangle$, $|\uparrow_{\bar{n}}\rangle \rightarrow |\uparrow_{\bar{p}}\downarrow_{\bar{e}}\rangle$, $|\uparrow_{\bar{n}}\rangle \rightarrow |\downarrow_{\bar{p}}\uparrow_{\bar{e}}\rangle$, $|\uparrow_{\bar{n}}\rangle \rightarrow |\uparrow_{\bar{p}}\uparrow_{\bar{e}}\rangle$, $|\downarrow_{\bar{n}}\rangle \rightarrow |\downarrow_{\bar{p}}\downarrow_{\bar{e}}\rangle$. So a deuteron and an anti-deuteron can experience a repulsive QS force if their spin-1 ($|\uparrow_p\rangle|\uparrow_n\rangle$) state is produced, in which case they will become unstable. Essentially, entanglement and conservation principles disallow the formation of triplet states of deuteron and anti-deuteron. The entangled transformations can be schematically described as

$$\begin{aligned}
|\psi_{\frac{1}{2}D}\bar{\psi}_{\frac{1}{2}D}\rangle_1 &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(|\psi_{\frac{1}{2}D}\rangle_1 |\bar{\psi}_{\frac{1}{2}D}\rangle_2 + |\psi_{\frac{1}{2}D}\rangle_2 |\bar{\psi}_{\frac{1}{2}D}\rangle_1) \\
&= \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(|\uparrow_n\rangle \cdot |\downarrow_p\rangle \cdot |\downarrow_{\bar{n}}\rangle \cdot |\uparrow_{\bar{p}}\rangle + |\downarrow_n\rangle \cdot |\uparrow_p\rangle \cdot |\uparrow_{\bar{n}}\rangle \cdot |\downarrow_{\bar{p}}\rangle) \\
&= \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(|\downarrow_p\uparrow_e\rangle|\downarrow_p\rangle \cdot |\uparrow_{\bar{p}}\downarrow_{\bar{e}}\rangle|\uparrow_{\bar{p}}\rangle + |\downarrow_p\uparrow_e\rangle|\uparrow_p\rangle \cdot |\uparrow_{\bar{p}}\downarrow_{\bar{e}}\rangle \cdot |\downarrow_{\bar{p}}\rangle) \\
&= \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(|\downarrow_p\rangle \cdot |\uparrow_e\downarrow_p\rangle \cdot |\uparrow_{\bar{p}}\rangle \cdot |\downarrow_{\bar{e}}\uparrow_{\bar{p}}\rangle + |\downarrow_p\uparrow_e\rangle|\uparrow_p\rangle \cdot |\uparrow_{\bar{p}}\downarrow_{\bar{e}}\rangle \cdot |\downarrow_{\bar{p}}\rangle) \\
&= \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(|\downarrow_p\rangle \cdot |\uparrow_n\rangle \cdot |\uparrow_{\bar{p}}\rangle \cdot |\downarrow_{\bar{n}}\rangle + |\downarrow_n\rangle \cdot |\uparrow_p\rangle \cdot |\uparrow_{\bar{n}}\rangle \cdot |\downarrow_{\bar{p}}\rangle) \\
&= \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(|\psi_{\frac{1}{2}D}\rangle_1 |\bar{\psi}_{\frac{1}{2}D}\rangle_2 + |\psi_{\frac{1}{2}D}\rangle_2 |\bar{\psi}_{\frac{1}{2}D}\rangle_1)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
|\psi_{\frac{1}{2}D}\bar{\psi}_{\frac{1}{2}D}\rangle_1 &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(|\downarrow_p\rangle \cdot |\uparrow_n\rangle \cdot |\uparrow_{\bar{p}}\rangle \cdot |\downarrow_{\bar{n}}\rangle + |\downarrow_n\rangle \cdot |\uparrow_p\rangle \cdot |\uparrow_{\bar{n}}\rangle \cdot |\downarrow_{\bar{p}}\rangle) \\
&= \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(|\downarrow_p\rangle \cdot |\uparrow_e\uparrow_p\rangle \cdot |\uparrow_{\bar{p}}\rangle \cdot |\downarrow_{\bar{e}}\downarrow_{\bar{p}}\rangle + |\downarrow_p\downarrow_e\rangle \cdot |\uparrow_p\rangle \cdot |\uparrow_{\bar{p}}\uparrow_{\bar{e}}\rangle \cdot |\downarrow_{\bar{p}}\rangle) \\
&= \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(|\downarrow_p\uparrow_e\rangle \cdot |\uparrow_p\rangle \cdot |\uparrow_{\bar{p}}\downarrow_{\bar{e}}\rangle \cdot |\downarrow_{\bar{p}}\rangle + |\downarrow_p\rangle \cdot |\downarrow_e\uparrow_p\rangle \cdot |\uparrow_{\bar{p}}\rangle \cdot |\uparrow_{\bar{e}}\downarrow_{\bar{p}}\rangle) \\
&= \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(|\downarrow_n\rangle \cdot |\uparrow_p\rangle \cdot |\uparrow_{\bar{n}}\rangle \cdot |\downarrow_{\bar{p}}\rangle + |\downarrow_p\rangle \cdot |\uparrow_n\rangle \cdot |\uparrow_{\bar{p}}\rangle \cdot |\downarrow_{\bar{n}}\rangle) \\
&= \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(|\psi_{\frac{1}{2}D}\rangle_2 |\bar{\psi}_{\frac{1}{2}D}\rangle_1 + |\psi_{\frac{1}{2}D}\rangle_1 |\bar{\psi}_{\frac{1}{2}D}\rangle_2)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
|\psi_{\frac{1}{2}D}\bar{\psi}_{\frac{1}{2}D}\rangle_2 &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(|\psi_{\frac{1}{2}D}\rangle_1 |\bar{\psi}_{\frac{1}{2}D}\rangle_1 + |\psi_{\frac{1}{2}D}\rangle_2 |\bar{\psi}_{\frac{1}{2}D}\rangle_2) \\
&= \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(|\uparrow_n\rangle|\downarrow_p\rangle|\uparrow_{\bar{n}}\rangle|\downarrow_{\bar{p}}\rangle + |\downarrow_n\rangle|\uparrow_p\rangle|\downarrow_{\bar{n}}\rangle|\uparrow_{\bar{p}}\rangle) \\
&= \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(|\downarrow_p\uparrow_e\rangle|\downarrow_p\rangle \cdot |\downarrow_{\bar{p}}\uparrow_{\bar{e}}\rangle|\downarrow_{\bar{p}}\rangle + |\uparrow_p\downarrow_e\rangle|\uparrow_p\rangle \cdot |\uparrow_{\bar{p}}\downarrow_{\bar{e}}\rangle|\uparrow_{\bar{p}}\rangle) \\
&= \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(|\downarrow_p\rangle \cdot |\uparrow_e\downarrow_p\rangle \cdot |\downarrow_{\bar{p}}\rangle \cdot |\uparrow_{\bar{e}}\downarrow_{\bar{p}}\rangle + |\uparrow_p\rangle \cdot |\downarrow_e\uparrow_p\rangle \cdot |\uparrow_{\bar{p}}\rangle|\uparrow_{\bar{e}}\uparrow_{\bar{p}}\rangle) \\
&= \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(|\downarrow_p\rangle \cdot |\uparrow_n\rangle \cdot |\downarrow_{\bar{p}}\rangle \cdot |\uparrow_{\bar{n}}\rangle + |\uparrow_p\rangle \cdot |\downarrow_n\rangle \cdot |\uparrow_{\bar{p}}\rangle|\downarrow_{\bar{n}}\rangle) \\
&= \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(|\psi_{\frac{1}{2}D}\rangle_1 |\bar{\psi}_{\frac{1}{2}D}\rangle_1 + |\psi_{\frac{1}{2}D}\rangle_2 |\bar{\psi}_{\frac{1}{2}D}\rangle_2)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
|\psi_{\frac{1}{2}D}\bar{\psi}_{\frac{1}{2}D}\rangle_2 &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(|\psi_{D_2}\rangle_1 |\bar{\psi}_{D_2}\rangle_1 + |\psi_{D_2}\rangle_2 |\bar{\psi}_{D_2}\rangle_2) \\
&= \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(|\uparrow_n\rangle|\downarrow_p\rangle|\uparrow_{\bar{n}}\rangle|\downarrow_{\bar{p}}\rangle + |\downarrow_n\rangle|\uparrow_p\rangle|\downarrow_{\bar{n}}\rangle|\uparrow_{\bar{p}}\rangle) \\
&= \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(|\uparrow_p\uparrow_e\rangle|\downarrow_p\rangle \cdot |\uparrow_{\bar{p}}\uparrow_{\bar{e}}\rangle|\downarrow_{\bar{p}}\rangle + |\downarrow_p\downarrow_e\rangle|\uparrow_p\rangle \cdot |\downarrow_{\bar{p}}\downarrow_{\bar{e}}\rangle|\uparrow_{\bar{p}}\rangle) \\
&= \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(|\uparrow_p\rangle \cdot |\uparrow_e\downarrow_p\rangle \cdot |\uparrow_{\bar{p}}\rangle \cdot |\uparrow_{\bar{e}}\downarrow_{\bar{p}}\rangle + |\downarrow_p\rangle \cdot |\downarrow_e\uparrow_p\rangle \cdot |\downarrow_{\bar{p}}\rangle|\downarrow_{\bar{e}}\uparrow_{\bar{p}}\rangle) \\
&= \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(|\uparrow_p\rangle \cdot |\downarrow_n\rangle \cdot |\uparrow_{\bar{p}}\rangle \cdot |\downarrow_{\bar{n}}\rangle + |\downarrow_p\rangle \cdot |\uparrow_n\rangle \cdot |\downarrow_{\bar{p}}\rangle|\uparrow_{\bar{n}}\rangle) \\
&= \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(|\psi_{\frac{1}{2}D}\rangle_2 |\bar{\psi}_{\frac{1}{2}D}\rangle_2 + |\psi_{\frac{1}{2}D}\rangle_1 |\bar{\psi}_{\frac{1}{2}D}\rangle_1)
\end{aligned}$$

Here, the transformation of the neutron and anti-neutron is entangled. To conserve spin angular momentum either $|\uparrow_n\rangle \rightarrow |\downarrow_p\uparrow_e\rangle$, $|\uparrow_n\rangle \rightarrow |\uparrow_p\downarrow_e\rangle$, $|\uparrow_{\bar{n}}\rangle \rightarrow |\uparrow_{\bar{p}}\downarrow_{\bar{e}}\rangle$, $|\uparrow_{\bar{n}}\rangle \rightarrow |\downarrow_{\bar{p}}\uparrow_{\bar{e}}\rangle$ or $|\uparrow_n\rangle \rightarrow |\uparrow_p\downarrow_e\rangle$, $|\uparrow_n\rangle \rightarrow |\uparrow_p\uparrow_e\rangle$, $|\uparrow_{\bar{n}}\rangle \rightarrow |\uparrow_{\bar{p}}\uparrow_{\bar{e}}\rangle$, $|\downarrow_{\bar{n}}\rangle \rightarrow |\downarrow_{\bar{p}}\downarrow_{\bar{e}}\rangle$ transformation will take place. In these transformations- $|\psi_{\frac{1}{2}D}\bar{\psi}_{\frac{1}{2}D}\rangle_1 \rightarrow |\psi_{\frac{1}{2}D}\bar{\psi}_{\frac{1}{2}D}\rangle_1$, $|\psi_{\frac{1}{2}D}\bar{\psi}_{\frac{1}{2}D}\rangle_2 \rightarrow |\psi_{\frac{1}{2}D}\bar{\psi}_{\frac{1}{2}D}\rangle_2$ - angular momentum conservation principle is not jointly violated, but it is separately violated during the neutrino-less neutron/anti-neutron decay and the electron/positron capture process. Due to entanglement, the QS force can produce a stable $\frac{1}{2}D \leftrightarrow \frac{1}{2}\bar{D}$ pair. Later, we shall see that quantum energy, E_q , can provide the required binding energy for the formation of this pair.

If $\frac{1}{2}D \leftrightarrow \frac{1}{2}\bar{D}$ pair is entangled through \bar{n} p pair, then its n is entangled with outside \bar{p} , and its \bar{p} is entangled with outside n. Thus, an entangled $\frac{1}{2}D \leftrightarrow \frac{1}{2}\bar{D}$ pair is also entangled with two outside nucleons/anti-nucleons. Each deuteron will be entangled with two anti-deuterons and vice versa. Two $\frac{1}{2}D \leftrightarrow \frac{1}{2}\bar{D}$ pair can be entangled and they can also be entangled with three outside nucleons/anti-nucleons. N entangled $\frac{1}{2}D \leftrightarrow \frac{1}{2}\bar{D}$ pairs are also entangled with N+1 free nucleons/anti-nucleons. Many $\frac{1}{2}D \leftrightarrow \frac{1}{2}\bar{D}$ pairs will be entangled among themselves with a linearly decreasing probability.

One entangled $\frac{1}{2}D \leftrightarrow \frac{1}{2}\bar{D}$ pair can synchronously fuse with another entangled $\frac{1}{2}D \leftrightarrow \frac{1}{2}\bar{D}$ pair locally to form an entangled helium nucleus and anti-helium nucleus, ${}^4_2\text{He} \leftrightarrow {}^4_2\bar{\text{He}}$, using common quantum energy through the entanglement channel. This simultaneous fusion is possible since N entangled

$\frac{1}{2}D \leftrightarrow \frac{1}{2}\bar{D}$ pairs are also entangled with N+1 free nucleons/anti-nucleons, as if the free nucleons/anti-nucleons act as an external glue. Thus, two-particle entanglement will convert into four-particle entanglement. Ultimately, two pairs of entangled deuteron and anti-deuteron can produce an entangled pair of helium and anti-helium ${}^4_2\text{He} \leftrightarrow {}^4_2\bar{\text{He}}$. On the platform of $|\psi_{\frac{1}{2}D}\bar{\psi}_{\frac{1}{2}D}\rangle_1$ and $|\psi_{\frac{1}{2}D}\bar{\psi}_{\frac{1}{2}D}\rangle_1$ the following two different entangled states of ${}^4_2\text{He} \leftrightarrow {}^4_2\bar{\text{He}}$ and ${}^3_2\text{He} \leftrightarrow {}^3_2\bar{\text{He}}$ can form.

$$|\psi_{{}^4_2\text{He}}\bar{\psi}_{{}^4_2\text{He}}\rangle_1 = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (|\psi_{\frac{1}{2}D}\bar{\psi}_{\frac{1}{2}D}\rangle_1 |\psi_{\frac{1}{2}D}\bar{\psi}_{\frac{1}{2}D}\rangle_2 + |\psi_{\frac{1}{2}D}\bar{\psi}_{\frac{1}{2}D}\rangle_2 |\psi_{\frac{1}{2}D}\bar{\psi}_{\frac{1}{2}D}\rangle_1)$$

$$|\psi_{{}^4_2\text{He}}\bar{\psi}_{{}^4_2\text{He}}\rangle_2 = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (|\psi_{\frac{1}{2}D}\bar{\psi}_{\frac{1}{2}D}\rangle_1 |\psi_{\frac{1}{2}D}\bar{\psi}_{\frac{1}{2}D}\rangle_1 + |\psi_{\frac{1}{2}D}\bar{\psi}_{\frac{1}{2}D}\rangle_2 |\psi_{\frac{1}{2}D}\bar{\psi}_{\frac{1}{2}D}\rangle_2)$$

$$|\psi_{{}^3_2\text{He}}\bar{\psi}_{{}^3_2\text{He}}\rangle_1 = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (|\psi_{\frac{1}{2}D}\bar{\psi}_{\frac{1}{2}D}\rangle_1 |\uparrow_p \downarrow_{\bar{p}}\rangle_2 + |\psi_{\frac{1}{2}D}\bar{\psi}_{\frac{1}{2}D}\rangle_2 |\uparrow_p \downarrow_{\bar{p}}\rangle_1)$$

$$|\psi_{{}^3_2\text{He}}\bar{\psi}_{{}^3_2\text{He}}\rangle_2 = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (|\psi_{\frac{1}{2}D}\bar{\psi}_{\frac{1}{2}D}\rangle_1 |\uparrow_p \downarrow_{\bar{p}}\rangle_1 + |\psi_{\frac{1}{2}D}\bar{\psi}_{\frac{1}{2}D}\rangle_2 |\uparrow_p \downarrow_{\bar{p}}\rangle_2)$$

One particle-anti-particle entanglement can be extended to many particle-anti-particle entanglement. All entangled nucleus and anti-nucleus $Z \leftrightarrow \bar{Z}$ will be formed on the platform of $\frac{1}{2}D \leftrightarrow \frac{1}{2}\bar{D}$. On its platform entangled nuclei and anti-nuclei will form. One particle-antiparticle entanglement can be extended to many particle-antiparticle entanglements. All entangled nuclei and anti-nuclei $Z \leftrightarrow \bar{Z}$ will be formed on the platform of $\frac{1}{2}D \leftrightarrow \frac{1}{2}\bar{D}$. On this platform, entangled nuclei and anti-nuclei will continue to form. The following two different entangled states of ${}^6_3\text{Li} \leftrightarrow {}^6_3\bar{\text{Li}}$, $\text{B}_{10} \leftrightarrow \bar{\text{B}}_{10}$, ${}^{10}_5\text{B} \leftrightarrow {}^{10}_5\bar{\text{B}}$, ${}^{12}_6\text{C} \leftrightarrow {}^{12}_6\bar{\text{C}}$, ${}^{13}_6\text{C} \leftrightarrow {}^{13}_6\bar{\text{C}}$, $\text{C}_{13} \leftrightarrow \bar{\text{C}}_{13}$, ${}^{16}_8\text{O} \leftrightarrow {}^{16}_8\bar{\text{O}}$ and ${}^a_r\text{Z} \leftrightarrow {}^a_r\bar{\text{Z}}$ can subsequently form.

$$|\psi_{{}^6_3\text{Li}}\bar{\psi}_{{}^6_3\text{Li}}\rangle_1 = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (|\psi_{{}^4_2\text{He}}\bar{\psi}_{{}^4_2\text{He}}\rangle_1 |\psi_{\frac{1}{2}D}\bar{\psi}_{\frac{1}{2}D}\rangle_2 + |\psi_{{}^4_2\text{He}}\bar{\psi}_{{}^4_2\text{He}}\rangle_2 |\psi_{\frac{1}{2}D}\bar{\psi}_{\frac{1}{2}D}\rangle_1)$$

$$|\psi_{{}^6_3\text{Li}}\bar{\psi}_{{}^6_3\text{Li}}\rangle_2 = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (|\psi_{{}^4_2\text{He}}\bar{\psi}_{{}^4_2\text{He}}\rangle_1 |\psi_{\frac{1}{2}D}\bar{\psi}_{\frac{1}{2}D}\rangle_2 + |\psi_{{}^4_2\text{He}}\bar{\psi}_{{}^4_2\text{He}}\rangle_2 |\psi_{\frac{1}{2}D}\bar{\psi}_{\frac{1}{2}D}\rangle_1)$$

$$|\psi_{{}^{10}_5\text{B}}\bar{\psi}_{{}^{10}_5\text{B}}\rangle_1 = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (|\psi_{{}^6_3\text{Li}}\bar{\psi}_{{}^6_3\text{Li}}\rangle_1 |\psi_{{}^4_2\text{He}}\bar{\psi}_{{}^4_2\text{He}}\rangle_2 + |\psi_{{}^6_3\text{Li}}\bar{\psi}_{{}^6_3\text{Li}}\rangle_2 |\psi_{{}^4_2\text{He}}\bar{\psi}_{{}^4_2\text{He}}\rangle_1)$$

$$|\psi_{{}^{10}_5\text{B}}\bar{\psi}_{{}^{10}_5\text{B}}\rangle_2 = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (|\psi_{{}^6_3\text{Li}}\bar{\psi}_{{}^6_3\text{Li}}\rangle_1 |\psi_{{}^4_2\text{He}}\bar{\psi}_{{}^4_2\text{He}}\rangle_1 + |\psi_{{}^6_3\text{Li}}\bar{\psi}_{{}^6_3\text{Li}}\rangle_2 |\psi_{{}^4_2\text{He}}\bar{\psi}_{{}^4_2\text{He}}\rangle_2)$$

$$|\psi_{{}^{12}_6\text{C}}\bar{\psi}_{{}^{12}_6\text{C}}\rangle_1 = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (|\psi_{{}^{10}_5\text{B}}\bar{\psi}_{{}^{10}_5\text{B}}\rangle_1 |\psi_{\frac{1}{2}D}\bar{\psi}_{\frac{1}{2}D}\rangle_2 + |\psi_{{}^{10}_5\text{B}}\bar{\psi}_{{}^{10}_5\text{B}}\rangle_2 |\psi_{\frac{1}{2}D}\bar{\psi}_{\frac{1}{2}D}\rangle_1)$$

$$|\psi_{{}^{12}_6\text{C}}\bar{\psi}_{{}^{12}_6\text{C}}\rangle_2 = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (|\psi_{{}^{10}_5\text{B}}\bar{\psi}_{{}^{10}_5\text{B}}\rangle_1 |\psi_{\frac{1}{2}D}\bar{\psi}_{\frac{1}{2}D}\rangle_1 + |\psi_{{}^{10}_5\text{B}}\bar{\psi}_{{}^{10}_5\text{B}}\rangle_2 |\psi_{\frac{1}{2}D}\bar{\psi}_{\frac{1}{2}D}\rangle_2)$$

$$|\psi_{{}^{13}_6\text{C}}\bar{\psi}_{{}^{13}_6\text{C}}\rangle_1 = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (|\psi_{{}^{11}_5\text{B}}\bar{\psi}_{{}^{11}_5\text{B}}\rangle_1 |\psi_{\frac{1}{2}D}\bar{\psi}_{\frac{1}{2}D}\rangle_2 + |\psi_{{}^{11}_5\text{B}}\bar{\psi}_{{}^{11}_5\text{B}}\rangle_2 |\psi_{\frac{1}{2}D}\bar{\psi}_{\frac{1}{2}D}\rangle_1)$$

$$|\psi_{{}^{13}_6\text{C}}\bar{\psi}_{{}^{13}_6\text{C}}\rangle_2 = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (|\psi_{{}^{11}_5\text{B}}\bar{\psi}_{{}^{11}_5\text{B}}\rangle_1 |\psi_{\frac{1}{2}D}\bar{\psi}_{\frac{1}{2}D}\rangle_1 + |\psi_{{}^{11}_5\text{B}}\bar{\psi}_{{}^{11}_5\text{B}}\rangle_2 |\psi_{\frac{1}{2}D}\bar{\psi}_{\frac{1}{2}D}\rangle_2)$$

$$|\psi_{{}^{16}_8\text{O}}\bar{\psi}_{{}^{16}_8\text{O}}\rangle_1 = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (|\psi_{{}^{12}_6\text{C}}\bar{\psi}_{{}^{12}_6\text{C}}\rangle_1 |\psi_{{}^4_2\text{He}}\bar{\psi}_{{}^4_2\text{He}}\rangle_2 + |\psi_{{}^{12}_6\text{C}}\bar{\psi}_{{}^{12}_6\text{C}}\rangle_2 |\psi_{{}^4_2\text{He}}\bar{\psi}_{{}^4_2\text{He}}\rangle_1)$$

$$|\psi_{16O} \bar{\psi}_{16O}\rangle_2 = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (|\psi_{12C} \bar{\psi}_{12C}\rangle_1 |\psi_{4He} \bar{\psi}_{4He}\rangle_1 + |\psi_{12C} \bar{\psi}_{12C}\rangle_2 |\psi_{4He} \bar{\psi}_{4He}\rangle_2)$$

$$|\psi_{rZ} \bar{\psi}_{rZ}\rangle_1 = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (|\psi_{pX} \bar{\psi}_{pX}\rangle_1 |\psi_{qY} \bar{\psi}_{qY}\rangle_2 + |\psi_{pX} \bar{\psi}_{pX}\rangle_2 |\psi_{qY} \bar{\psi}_{qY}\rangle_1)$$

$$|\psi_{rZ} \bar{\psi}_{rZ}\rangle_2 = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (|\psi_{pX} \bar{\psi}_{pX}\rangle_1 |\psi_{qY} \bar{\psi}_{qY}\rangle_1 + |\psi_{pX} \bar{\psi}_{pX}\rangle_2 |\psi_{qY} \bar{\psi}_{qY}\rangle_2)$$

where

$${}^a_rZ = {}^b_pX + {}^c_qY$$

Each nucleus and anti-nucleus will have two entangled states. Not all nuclei and anti-nuclei will form solely on the platform of $|\psi_{1D} \bar{\psi}_{1D}\rangle_1$ and $|\psi_{1D} \bar{\psi}_{1D}\rangle_2$. Entanglement provides stability to nuclei and anti-nuclei. Stable $N \leftrightarrow \bar{N}$ are produced by a synchronous complete fusion reaction: $X + Y = Z \leftrightarrow \bar{Z} = \bar{X} + \bar{Y}$ when X, Y, \bar{X} and \bar{Y} are stable. Since X and \bar{X} are stable, they are entangled. Similarly, since Y and \bar{Y} are stable, they are also entangled. Thus, two entangled pairs will synchronously create a higher entangled pair $Z \leftrightarrow \bar{Z}$.

Stable nuclei and anti-nuclei are produced through asynchronous nuclear reactions: $X + Y \rightarrow Z + W$. The question is how an asynchronous reaction provides stability to X and W. After synchronous production via a complete fusion reaction, Z and W can be produced asynchronously because they become entangled with their corresponding anti-nuclei produced in the synchronous reaction. Thus, asynchronous reactions ensure stability through the quantum indistinguishability principle. After the synchronous production of one element, the second production can occur asynchronously due to the same principle.

Some stable nuclei /anti-nuclei are asynchronously produced through electron/positron capture : $X + e = Z \leftrightarrow \bar{Z} = \bar{X} + \bar{e}$ and some through positron/electron emission $X + \bar{e} = Z \leftrightarrow \bar{Z} = \bar{X} + e$. Here Z and \bar{Z} become entangled because stable nucleus X and anti-nucleus \bar{X} are synchronously produced by complete fusion reactions. The production of stable nucleus/anti-nucleus is possible only through these three processes. Through electron/positron capture and positron/electron emission, more and more neutron/antineutron can be added to different nuclei/anti-nuclei produced by the complete fusion of stable nuclei/anti-nuclei. ${}^7_3Li \leftrightarrow {}^7_3\bar{Li}$, produced by the electron/positron capture process plays a crucial role in the production of neutron anti-neutron enriched elements and anti-elements. An unstable element can be produced by the complete fusion of stable elements and by beta or alpha emission.

In consistency with the model, so far no stable nucleus Z has been asynchronously produced through complete fusion reactions in the laboratory: $X + Y \neq Z$. In consistency with the model, we have observed that all stable nuclei can be produced through any of the three processes, as given in Table 1. Apart from hydrogen, the number of stable or observably stable elements is 246.

5. Entangled Energy: According to our model, quantum energy is the energy to confine virtual neutron anti-neutron in a qtom. We know that $\nabla p \cdot \nabla x = h/2\pi \cdot E_q = \frac{p^2}{2m}$, where m is total mass of $n-\bar{n}$ pair and p is their momentum. For $\nabla x \approx 2 \cdot 10^{-12}$, we get $E_q \approx 5$ MeV. For the fusion of different stable elements, a minimum of 0.38 MeV and a maximum of 25 MeV energy is required to overcome the Coulomb barrier, E_c , without any help from quantum tunneling. A pair of $\frac{1}{2}D \leftrightarrow \frac{1}{2}\bar{D}$ is also entangled with one free proton and one free stable anti-neutron or one free anti-proton and one free stable neutron. N entangled $\frac{1}{2}D \leftrightarrow \frac{1}{2}\bar{D}$ pairs can additionally become entangled with 2N free nucleons/anti-nucleons (N neutrons/antineutron and N antiproton/proton with equal probability). The free protons will be accumulated due to attractive QC force exerted by the entangled electrons. Similarly, the free protons will be accumulated due to attractive QC force exerted by the entangled positrons. The N free stable neutrons and antineutrons that remain can supply the required quantum energy to overcome E_c . 6 $\frac{1}{2}D \leftrightarrow \frac{1}{2}\bar{D}$ pairs will be additionally entangled with 12 free nucleons/anti-nucleons. Thus, 3 free neutrons and 3 free anti-neutrons will have access of a total $E_Q \approx 30$ MeV which is enough for the synthesis of elements and anti-elements, provided this energy can be shared.

Spin entanglement does not imply energy entanglement. A neutron–antineutron pair has no entangled energy state, but their energy may be considered entangled. Spin-wise entangled neutrons and antineutrons are generated with confinement energy from qtom. Confinement energy is not the individual energy of the neutron or antineutron; it is the shared energy of the neutron–antineutron pair. Both can use this energy jointly while obeying energy conservation: $E_q := E_i^n + E_j^{\bar{n}} = E_j^n + E_i^{\bar{n}}$. Later, with the creation of $|\psi_n \bar{\psi}_n\rangle_{21}$ or $|\psi_n \bar{\psi}_n\rangle_{22}$ the confinement energy will be shared among stable neutron, antiproton, positron or stable anti-neutron, proton and electron. With the formation of entangled deuterons and anti-deuterons, multi-particle entanglement is established, and the shared energy also increases exponentially. This confinement energy is accessible to the entire entangled chain of particles and antiparticles, and can be used by any of them if required, as if the others in the entangled chain supply the energy. Due to entanglement, all elements and anti-elements can be synthesized by quantum energy in the matter–antimatter cloud without the help of the quantum tunneling effect. In different nuclear fusion reactions, the maximum released energy is ~ 24 MeV, which is the Q value. Entangled energy can be the source of the Q value, but quantum energy is used to overcome E_c . For any fusion reaction, $E_c + Q$ is less than 30 MeV. Quantum energy is used both for the formation of elements/anti-elements and for energy generation. No energy can be created from the mass of a particle. No mass can be created by increasing the energy of a particle. In annihilation, a particle and its corresponding antiparticle, along with their mass, charge, and spin, are destroyed and converted into energy and momentum. Needless to say, mass, spin, and charge are not equivalent to energy and momentum.

Let us check whether E_q can generate enormous heat in stars. The sun contains $\approx 10^{57}$ particles, so it contains $E_q \approx 10^{57}$ MeV energy. Thus the average energy density of the sun is about 10^{26} MeV/c.c. $\approx 10^{32}$ eV/c.c 1, which corresponds to roughly 10^8 K (assuming only 1% of E_q is deposited). Therefore E_q can supply heat energy to the sun. It implies that confinement energy can be regarded as quantum energy. The detection of extremely energetic cosmic particle (of the order of

10^{20} eV, is another possible indication a particle can gain enormous energy due to shared entanglement.

6. Energy density : According to our model, the energy density of the universe is the total quantum energy density which equals to total number density of neutron-anti-neutron pairs multiplied by the quantum energy carried by each neutron-anti-neutron pair.

$$\rho_E \sim \frac{N_n E_q}{V}$$

At r-th epoch, the number of neutron-antineutron is, $N_n \approx 2^{\frac{2r}{3}}$ and V is the volume of the universe. At the current epoch, the total number of qatoms is $N \approx 10^{120}$. So the number of generated neutron/antineutron is $N_n \sim 2^{\frac{2r}{3}} \approx 10^{80}$. Total Energy $E \approx N_n E_q \approx 10^{80}$ MeV. The total volume of the universe $V = N \cdot v \approx 10^{120} \cdot v$ where v is the volume of a qatom. In the present epoch, $\rho_E \approx \frac{10^{80}}{10^{120}} \frac{E_q}{v} \approx 10^{-40} 10^{44} \text{ MeV/m}^3 \approx 10^{-9} \text{ J/m}^3$. In this current epoch, the estimated energy density $\rho_E \approx 10^{-9} \text{ J/m}^3$. This shows excellent agreement between the predicted and observed values. The model can resolve the long-standing disagreement regarding the energy density of the universe.

7. Quantum Mass Force: According to our model, the quantum mass (QM) force is activated in a qatom with probability P_m . Two particles can experience QM force if they are directly or indirectly entangled. The probability of two particles, separated by distance R, getting entangled is $P_{en} = 1/R^2$ since particles spread spherically after getting separated and solid angle subtended by a unit area is the measure of the probability of the two particles of being entangled, which is proportional to $1/R^2 \propto \frac{1}{N_R^2}$, where N_R is the number of qatoms occupying the intervening distance R. Two bodies will experience QM force with total probability P which is the product of the probability, P_{en} , of entanglement and probability, P_m , of activation of the QM force.

The number of particles associated with a body is proportional to the mass of the body: $M \propto N_M$; $m \propto N_m$. From probabilistic point of view, force may be considered as force-score. Gravitational force can be expressed from the probabilistic concept of force.

$$F_m \sim N_M \cdot N_m \cdot P_m \cdot P_{en} = \frac{N_M N_m}{N_R^2} P_m \equiv G \frac{M, m}{R^2}$$

Let us try to assess the probability P_m . Planets and asteroids contain large number of particles experiencing the QM force due to the sun. But asteroids are unstable, so F_m can be assumed to be nearly 1. To assess P_m an asteroid may be useful. For a small asteroid, weighing $\approx 10^6$ Kg, $N_m \approx 10^{33}$. For the sun $N_M \approx 10^{57}$, and $N_R \approx 10^{26}$, as the distance between an asteroid in the asteroid belt and the sun is $\approx 10^{13}$ cm. Putting the values into $F_m \sim \frac{N_M N_m}{N_R^2} P_m$, we get $P_m \approx 10^{-38}$. Similarly, artificial satellite has no stable orbit, so its $F_m \approx 1$. The weight of a small satellite is ~ 1000 kg, and its distance from earth is $\sim 10^4$ km. Here, $N_M \approx 10^{52}$, $N_m \approx 10^{30}$, $N_R \approx 10^{22}$. Substituting the values, we again get $P_m \approx 10^{-38}$. Interestingly, the value of P_m also limits the orbital velocity of celestial bodies.

Later, we shall assess the activation probabilities, P_s and P_c for QS force and QC forces, respectively and see that $P_s + P_c + P_m \approx 1$.

8. Quantum Planetary Motion: For planets we expect a high force-score for highly stable systems such as sun-earth and earth-moon systems, and the orbital velocity will not exceed C . For sun-earth pair we estimate, $N_M \approx 10^{57}$, $N_m \approx 3 \times 10^{51}$, $N_R \approx 10^{26}$ giving $F_m \sim 10^{19}$. Using this calculated force score, a planet's orbital period and velocity can be predicted. The orbital period of a planet can be considered as the product of q_{tim} and the number of q_{tims} required for all particles of the sun-planet system to experience QM force during one revolution of the planet. The force-score may expressed as $F_m = m \omega^2 r \equiv N_m \cdot \frac{4\pi^2}{N_T^2} N_R$. The time period is $T = N_T \cdot \nabla t$, and the orbital velocity is $v = \frac{2\pi N_R \nabla x}{N_T \cdot \nabla t}$ where N_T is the number of q_{tims} . In table below lists the calculated orbital periods alongside the observed orbital periods for planets and some selected moons.

	M	N_M	N_m	N_R	F_m	N_T	T_{Cal}	v in m/s	$\sim T_{Obs}$
Sun	Mercury	10^{57}	10^{51}	10^{25}	10^{20}	10^{29}	10^5 sec	10^4	10^6 sec
Sun	Venus	10^{57}	10^{52}	10^{26}	10^{19}	10^{30}	10^6 sec	10^4	10^7 sec
Sun	Earth	10^{57}	10^{52}	10^{26}	10^{19}	10^{30}	10^6 sec	10^4	10^7 sec
Sun	Mars	10^{57}	10^{51}	10^{26}	10^{18}	10^{30}	10^6 sec	10^4	10^7 sec
Sun	Jupiter	10^{57}	10^{55}	10^{27}	10^{20}	10^{31}	10^7 sec	10^4	10^8 sec
Sun	Saturn	10^{57}	10^{54}	10^{27}	10^{19}	10^{31}	10^7 sec	10^3	10^8 sec
Sun	Uranus	10^{57}	10^{54}	10^{27}	10^{19}	10^{32}	10^8 sec	10^3	10^9 sec
Sun	Neptune	10^{57}	10^{54}	10^{27}	10^{19}	10^{32}	10^8 sec	10^3	10^9 sec
Earth	Moon	10^{52}	10^{50}	10^{23}	10^{18}	10^{28}	10^4 sec	10^3	10^5 sec
Jupiter	Metis	10^{55}	10^{42}	10^{23}	10^{13}	10^{26}	10^3 sec	10^4	10^4 sec
Jupiter	Pasiphae	10^{55}	10^{43}	10^{25}	10^{10}	10^{29}	10^6 sec	10^3	10^7 sec

Orbital periods are consistent with observed values. The orbital velocities of planets and moons did not exceed C . Kepler's law can also be verified using the predicted order of the number of q_{toms} and q_{tims} corresponding to the semi-major axis and orbital period of Mercury and Neptune, as well as Metis and Pasiphae. Therefore, Kepler's law may be rephrased as

Quantum Kepler's law: The square of the number of q_{tims} for a planet's orbital period is directly proportional to the cube of the number of q_{toms} in its semi-major axis

$$N_T^2 \propto N_R^3$$

Let us try to understand how planets acquired this motion [14]. In addition to the attractive QM force, the Sun and planets can experience a repulsive QS force because they share entangled electron-proton pairs with some probability. The inward attractive QM force can act at an angle with the outward

repulsive QS force. As a result, the resultant force can be tangential, which is required for the orbital motion of planets. Essentially, the particles that formed the planets experienced such a resultant tangential force. Thus, the orbital motion of a pro-planet is initiated by two quantum forces jointly. The repulsive QS force initiates orbital motion, but it is also essential for rotational motion. A proton/electron of the planet can experience the attractive QM force, while another entangled proton/electron of the planet can simultaneously experience the repulsive QS force.

These two equal and opposite forces can produce a micro-torque in a planet, causing the planet to spin around an axis where maximum torque is generated by all such pairs. QM and QS forces can initiate the spinning motion of a planet, since these equal and opposite forces can act at two different points and thus produce torque. It may be noted that the distribution of entangled protons and electrons is not necessarily spherically symmetric in planets, which themselves may not be perfectly spherical. Such distributions between a star and its different planets will lie more or less in the same plane. It can be expected that all planets will revolve in the same plane, and their orbits may be elliptical or circular. In our solar system, most planets are not spherical. In other planetary systems as well, most planets revolve in the same plane. Later, we shall examine whether the total spin angular momentum of entangled proton–electron pairs shared between a planet and its star can generate both the orbital and rotational angular momentum of the planet. This can either falsify or strengthen the interpretation.

9. Stability of Stars: Quantum mechanics does not allow the permanent destruction of all nuclei, atoms, and molecules, since they are quantum states. Therefore, quantum mechanics does not permit the destruction of galactic structures along with their constituent nuclei, atoms, and molecules. A galactic structure can survive indefinitely if its stars can survive indefinitely with some probability. Stars can survive indefinitely if they can continuously generate energy. This is possible if nuclear reactions can cyclically occur in stars forever, aided by some hidden energy source. Entanglement is the hidden source that can sustain cyclic nuclear reactions indefinitely in stars. Within a galaxy, all stars become entangled because they share certain entangled particles or nuclei. Similarly, all galaxies become entangled through shared entangled particles or nuclei. The universe thus forms a web of entangled galaxies.

Due to radiation, stars and galaxies lose some energy linearly over time. However, new particles are created linearly in newly formed galaxies. These new galaxies can compensate for the lost energy of matter and antimatter stars in old galaxies through the entanglement channel. Consequently, new galaxies can supply the necessary quantum energy to all old stars, allowing stars to shine at a constant rate. Entanglement acts as a quantum tunnel through which energy continuously reaches stars and anti-stars. Stars and anti-stars can synchronously produce energy in a self-sustaining process due to the energy supplied by new galaxies through the entanglement channel. As a result, the universe will not proceed toward heat death. The unitarity of quantum mechanics prevents the heat death of the universe.

The observed number of unstable stars is significantly less than the number of active stars. This number indicates statistical fluctuations in their stability parameters. In nature, hierarchical or pyramidal

structures are generally formed to increase stability. The existence of hierarchical galactic structures containing clusters, superclusters, and filaments perhaps implies that structures are not bound to collapse ever. For many decades, researchers have been trying to produce fusion energy based on the classical nucleosynthesis model. In a fusion reactor, the asynchronous fusion reaction rate will decrease linearly with time since the reaction cannot be recycled. Self-sustaining fusion cannot be achieved artificially. Despite tremendous effort, self-sustaining fusion has not been achieved. This failure possibly supports the model.

10. Evolution of Galactic Structure: Galaxies will arrange themselves so that they can remain stable, overcoming the attractive QM force. A group of matter galaxies will experience the attractive QM force because they share entangled protons and electrons. By experiencing the attractive QM force and sharing quantum energy, a group of matter galaxies can move closer to each other and eventually form the smallest galactic structure (GS). Similarly, a group of antimatter galaxies can form the smallest GS. In a GS, galaxies will orbit around a common barycenter and spin around an axis due to the combined action of the attractive QM force and the repulsive QS force. As more and more galaxies form, the number of such GS structures will increase.

Similarly, by experiencing attractive QM forces and sharing quantum energy, a group of GS can approach each other and eventually form higher GS. In this way, more and more matter and antimatter hierarchical GS can form. Since the QM force decreases with the square of the distance, it can be expected that the number of substructures will increase quadratically to form a structure. The smallest GS, say a_0 -th, GS can contain only 2 galaxies: 2 a_0 -th GS can form the a_1 -th GS; 2^2 a_1 -th GS will form a_2 -th GS; 2^4 a_2 -th GS will form a_3 -th GS; 2^8 a_3 -th GS will form a_4 -th GS; 2^{16} a_4 -th GS will form a_5 -th GS. In general, 2^{2^m} a_{m-1} -th GS will form the highest a_m -th GS. The number of different GS will be m when $2^f = 2^{2^m}$ number of galaxies form. In a similar way, simultaneously, different series of GS can form on the smallest structures of 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, ... galaxies as $2^x \approx 3^b \approx 4^c \approx 5^d \approx 6^e \approx 7^f \approx 8^g$. That is, 6^{2^m} galaxies can form the highest a_m -th GS based on the smallest structure containing 6 galaxies. Therefore, during initial formation of GS, re-clustering of GS can occur. Due to the hierarchical nature, only the highest matter GS will be adjacent to the highest antimatter GS.

According to our estimation, in the present epoch, the number of galaxies and anti-galaxies will be $\sim 2^{36}$ and $m \sim 5$. At present, the formation of GS is in its infancy. At the 364th epoch, the number of particles became sufficient for the formation of a galaxy and an anti-galaxy. Between the 364th and 384th epochs, $\sim 10^6$ galaxies were formed, between $\sim 10^1$ to $\sim 10^2$ million years after quantum quiet. Our universe will bloom with galaxies and stars. At the 1000th epoch, the number of galaxies will be $\sim 2^{636}$, and the number of different HGS will then be $m \sim 9$. This will take $\sim 10^{25}$ billion years to form. If all galaxies are distributed in one galactic structure, the Shannon entropy of the distribution would be 2^{2^m} . The Shannon entropy of the distribution of galaxies in the m -th GS will be $2m$ bits. This represents an enormous reduction of entropy. GS will revolve around its common barycenter for stability. In

addition, GS will rotate around an axis. However, GS will exhibit orbital and rotational motion only when its immediate higher GS is completely formed, because to generate motion, GS requires enormous angular momentum.

It has been observed that in the cosmic web, GS are hierarchical. Different GS, such as galaxy pairs, compact small groups, subgroups, local clusters, clusters, superclusters, filaments, etc., have been observed. Smaller GS containing 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, or 10 galaxies have been detected. That is, apart from smaller GS, 4 to 5 larger GS have also been found. Based on the collected data, the estimated number of observed galaxies at present is $\sim 2^{32}$, and the estimated time of initial galaxy formation is about 100 to 500 million years after the creation of the universe.

The observed numbers of clusters, superclusters, and filaments decrease nearly exponentially. Orbital and spinning motions of groups of galaxies have been detected. No orbital motion of filaments has been detected. Some signatures of rotational motion in clusters, superclusters, and filaments [19,20] have been detected. All these observations are consistent with the model.

11. Angular Momentum: Moons, planets, stars, galaxies, and GS, etc. possess enormous angular momentum. However, its source is still not known. According to our model, entangled neutrons and anti-neutrons possess spin angular momentum—some of this spin angular momentum is transferred to the electron-proton pair and the positron–anti-proton pair. Let us see whether this can be the source of the rotational angular momentum of celestial bodies. The spin angular momentum of an entangled electron-proton pair $\frac{\sqrt{3}h}{2\pi}$. Rotational angular-momentum score of two entangled celestial bodies is by $L_R = P_{en} \cdot \frac{\sqrt{3}h}{2\pi} \cdot N_1 N_2$, where N_1 is the number of proton/electron of body 1, and N_2 is the number of electron/proton of body 2, and P_{en} is the maximum probability of body 1 and body 2 sharing an entangled proton and electron along any direction and plane. For sun-earth system, the rotational angular momentum stored is, $L_R = 10^{-38} \frac{\sqrt{3}h}{2\pi} 10^{109} \sim 10^{37} \text{ kg m}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$ where $P_{en} = P_m = 10^{-38}$. In the following table, we compare orbital and rotational angular momentum, L_o and L_r with L_R of different planetary systems.

	L_R	L_o	L_r
Sun–Earth	$\sim 10^{37} \text{ kg m}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$	$\sim 10^{40} \text{ kg m}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$	$\sim 10^{33} \text{ kg m}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$
Sun–Mercury	$\sim 10^{36} \text{ kg m}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$	$\sim 10^{38} \text{ kg m}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$	$\sim 10^{26} \text{ kg m}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$
Sun–Venus	$\sim 10^{37} \text{ kg m}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$	$\sim 10^{40} \text{ kg m}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$	$\sim 10^{31} \text{ kg m}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$
Sun–Mars	$\sim 10^{36} \text{ kg m}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$	$\sim 10^{39} \text{ kg m}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$	$\sim 10^{32} \text{ kg m}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$
Sun–Jupiter	$\sim 10^{40} \text{ kg m}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$	$\sim 10^{43} \text{ kg m}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$	$\sim 10^{38} \text{ kg m}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$
Sun–Uranus	$\sim 10^{39} \text{ kg m}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$	$\sim 10^{42} \text{ kg m}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$	$\sim 10^{36} \text{ kg m}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$
Sun–Neptune	$\sim 10^{39} \text{ kg m}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$	$\sim 10^{42} \text{ kg m}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$	$\sim 10^{36} \text{ kg m}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$
Earth–Moon	$\sim 10^{30} \text{ kg m}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$	$\sim 10^{34} \text{ kg m}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$	$\sim 10^{29} \text{ kg m}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$

Mars-Phobos	$\sim 10^{22} \text{ kg m}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$	$\sim 10^{26} \text{ kg m}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$	$\sim 10^{21} \text{ kg m}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$
Jupiter-Ganymede	$\sim 10^{33} \text{ kg m}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$	$\sim 10^{34} \text{ kg m}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$	$\sim 10^{30} \text{ kg m}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$

In all cases, $L_R < L_o$ and $L_R > L_r$. The rotational angular momentum of planets and moons can be provided by L_R , but the orbital angular momentum cannot. However, the Sun can supply the required orbital angular momentum to the Moon, since the Moon and the Sun also share an entangled proton–electron pair. Similarly, the galactic core can provide orbital angular momentum to the Earth.

12. Temperature : Due to collisions among particles and antiparticles, a percentage of quantum energy is converted into heat energy. The generated heat will exponentially decrease in successive epochs with the expansion of the universe. According to our model, as mass density exponentially decreases in successive epochs, the generated heat will also exponentially decrease. Heat generated in previous epochs contributes equally with the heat generated in the ongoing epoch. In each epoch, photons and matter–antimatter particles are in thermal equilibrium, with constant scattering, emission, and absorption. The generated heat will form a perfect blackbody.

According to our model, CMB is a mixture of relic radiation generated in the previous epochs contributing equally, and fresh radiation generated in the ongoing epoch. Let us check whether generated heat can be considered as CMB. According to our estimation and observation, the present epoch, the quantum energy density is $\rho_E \approx 10^{-9} \text{ J/m}^3 \sim 1 \text{ eV/c.c.}$ Three particles/antiparticles will lose their quantum energy with different proportions. The energy loss of a $\sim 1 \text{ MeV}$ proton/neutron in collision is nearly ~ 1 to 0.1% . If the quantum energy loss becomes 1% , then the total deposited energy density will be $\sim 0.1 \text{ eV/c.c.} \sim 1 \text{ K}$. The observed temperature of CMB radiation is $\sim 2.7 \text{ K}$. The estimated/observed temperature is consistent with CMB data. At 1000^{th} epoch, the temperature of the universe will be $\sim 10^{-60} \text{ K}$ after $\sim 10^{25}$ billion years.

13. Dark matter: According to our model, some percentage of stable neutrons and antineutrons will not be able to contribute any luminous mass. The observed ratio of neutrons to protons in the present universe is 1:6 (this is also the unobserved ratio of antineutrons to antiprotons). It implies that the amount of missing stable neutrons and antineutrons will be on the order of the visible mass. A simple calculation can show that missing stable neutrons and antineutrons within a galaxy or anti-galaxy can explain the rotational curve, provided the luminous mass is also underestimated. According to the classical nucleosynthesis model, stars generate energy at the cost of their mass, and luminosity is a measure of stellar mass. According to the quantum nucleosynthesis model, a fraction of shared quantum energy is released through a nuclear reaction, and that energy is not stored in the luminous mass alone. Therefore, luminosity cannot be a measure of stellar or galactic mass. On the basis of the classical nucleosynthesis model, the luminous mass of a galaxy or anti-galaxy has been underestimated. Our model concludes that stable, missing neutrons and antineutrons constitute the dark matter. It also explains the asymmetry in the number density of neutrons/antineutrons and protons/antiprotons in the current universe.

14. Horizon and Flatness Problem: According to our model, in each epoch, the speed of expansion of the entire length of space is $C/2$. The generation of qtons and of particles/antiparticles started with different probabilities at the same time. Since the optimal speed of a particle is $C/2$, CMB radiation generated at any point in space due to collision or scattering can reach the opposite sides of the horizon over the total evolutionary time of the universe. The temperature of the universe will be uniform throughout. The universe is not flat; it is spherically symmetric because the probability of qtom generation is the same in all directions. The space-sphere is not smooth; space will have distortions due to statistical fluctuations in the generation of qtons at each point. Like most cosmological problems, the horizon and flatness problems are not evolutionary problems—they arise from Big Bang cosmology.

15. Matter-Antimatter Asymmetry : According to our model, there is no matter–antimatter asymmetry. In the current epoch, matter and antimatter galactic filaments will be adjacent. Because of the large void (330 to 500 million light-years) between a filament and its corresponding anti-filament, the chance of matter–antimatter annihilation along their boundary will be an extremely rare event. This may explain why frequent annihilation events have not been observed in intergalactic or anti-galactic space. Matter–antimatter asymmetry will be observed within a filament or anti-filament. Detection of large clouds of antimatter [21,22] within our matter galaxy also supports the model, as it indicates that antimatter can be created within matter structures and vice versa. Detection of electron–positron annihilation gamma rays by AMS-02 on the ISS [23], tentative detection of anti-helium by AMS-02 on the ISS [24], and observation of antimatter annihilation signatures [25] in the detected BOAT gamma rays are all supportive of the model.

According to the model, since there is no matter–antimatter asymmetry, there is no gravity–antigravity asymmetry. If such asymmetry does not exist, a large cloud of antimatter can form within a matter structure due to the attractive QM force acting among antiparticles and the repulsive QM force acting between matter and antimatter particles. The observed antimatter cloud [21,22] within a matter galaxy may be considered indirect evidence of the existence of antigravity. However, in one experiment, antigravity was not observed [26]. Staying in a matter GS, it is a challenging task to observe antigravity between a particle and an antiparticle while suppressing the QS force, since it is not a short-range force. Without the symmetric evolution of the universe, the GS would have collapsed.

16. Radioactivity: Entanglement can provide partial stability to nuclei and anti-nuclei. An unstable nucleus is the direct product of an entangled state and an unentangled state, which can provide partial stability. The unstable nucleus will try to form a completely stable entangled state by emitting a beta/anti-beta particle, capturing an electron/positron, or emitting an alpha/anti-alpha particle. Asynchronous neutrino-less beta decay violates this principle, but the beta-emitter jointly obeys the principle with the entangled anti-nucleus. Similarly, a free neutron is not truly free—it is entangled with another anti-nucleus. The decay of a free neutron violates the angular momentum conservation principle, but it jointly obeys the principle with the entangled anti-nucleus.

Beta/anti-beta or alpha/anti-alpha can disentangle from the remaining constituent with probability P_R . An entangled nucleus/anti-nucleus will decay with probability P_R . Disintegration occurs as a result of disentanglement. The nucleus/anti-nucleus will not disintegrate (or disentangle) for about $\frac{1}{P_R}$ number of neutron/anti-neutron life-times with probability close to 1. On average, the survival time of a radioactive nucleus/anti-nucleus is $T \sim \frac{\tau_n}{P_R}$ which is approximately equal to its half-life.

$$t_{\frac{1}{2}} \sim \frac{\tau_n}{P_R}$$

In the case of beta emission, a neutron is not entangled with the remaining entangled state. The neutron splits into an electron and a proton. If the spins of the electron and its entangled proton are the same, the electron can be captured by another proton with the opposite spin. The probability of capture by a single proton is 1/4. The probability of capture by maximum m number of permanent and converted protons of the entangled state is $P_R = 2^{-2m}$. In the case of alpha emission, a single proton or neutron alone cannot hold an alpha particle. A nucleus with mass number 5 does not exist. A pair of alpha and anti-alpha particles can get disentangled from the remaining entangled pair with probability 1/4. In alpha and anti-alpha emitters, alpha and anti-alpha emission takes place with a minimum probability $P_R = 2^{-2m}$ where m is the number of remaining such pairs. The half-life of a radioactive nucleus can be predicted if we know in how many ways it is produced and with what probability.

Tritium is a beta emitter that is produced mainly from ($n, {}^7_3\text{Li}$) reaction. So tritium is entangled with ${}^7_3\text{Li} \leftrightarrow {}^7_3\bar{\text{Li}}$. For tritium, $P_R = 2^{-14}$. $t_{\frac{1}{2}} \approx 3$ years. The observed $t_{\frac{1}{2}} \approx 12$ years. Similarly, C14 is a beta emitter that is produced from the ($n, \text{N-14}$) reaction. So C-14 is entangled with ${}^{14}_7\text{N} \leftrightarrow {}^{14}_7\bar{\text{N}}$. $P_R = 2^{-28}$. $t_{\frac{1}{2}} \approx 7000$ years. The observed $t_{\frac{1}{2}} \approx 5040$ years. The model can explain the long half-life of carbon-14. The alpha emitter with lowest Z will have longest half-life. ${}^{209}_{83}\text{Bi}$, has been found to be the alpha emitter with lowest Z . Its quantum state is, $|\psi_{209\text{Bi}} \bar{\psi}_{209\text{Bi}}\rangle_1 = |\psi_{205\text{Tl}} \bar{\psi}_{205\text{Tl}}\rangle_1 |\psi_{4\text{He}} \bar{\psi}_{4\text{He}}\rangle_1$. For ${}^{209}_{83}\text{Bi}$, $m=40$, $P_R = 2^{-80}$. $t_{\frac{1}{2}} \approx 10^{19}$ years. The observed $t_{\frac{1}{2}} \approx 2.1 \times 10^{19}$ years. In these cases observed and predicted values are in good agreement.

Due to matter–antimatter symmetry in the universe, a matter particle alone cannot be converted into an antimatter particle, and vice versa—they can only be produced jointly through pair production. Let us now explain positron emission. Positron emission occurs via electron capture and pair production. The same radioactive element can undergo electron capture: $p + e \rightarrow n$ and positron emission through electron capture followed by pair production: $p + e \rightarrow n + \gamma \rightarrow n + ee^+$ with different probabilities, provided that the energy difference between the entangled parent and daughter atom is greater than 1.022 MeV. The gamma photon can produce an electron–positron pair in and around the nucleus, and the electron from the pair can either be emitted or annihilate with any other emitted positrons. Experimental data from the two processes do not contradict the proposition that positron emission is a secondary process of electron capture.

17. Quantum atomic and chemical synthesis : Like quantum nucleo-synthesis, atom and molecules are also synthesized through quantum processes. Due to the formation of $|\psi_n\bar{\psi}_n\rangle_{21}$, an entangled electron and proton can experience attractive QC force and a repulsive QS force. However, it is unlikely that an entangled proton-electron pair will approach closely enough to form a hydrogen atom directly. After the formation of many entangled $\frac{1}{2}D \leftrightarrow \frac{1}{2}\bar{D}$ pairs, free protons can become entangled with nearby free electrons, since they can, in turn, entangle with the entangled $\frac{1}{2}D \leftrightarrow \frac{1}{2}\bar{D}$ pairs. Similarly, entanglement can be indirectly established with free positrons and free anti-protons. In essence, entanglement among protons, electrons, positrons, and anti-protons can be established through entangled $\frac{1}{2}D \leftrightarrow \frac{1}{2}\bar{D}$ pairs.

So entangled hydrogen and anti-hydrogen can synchronously form. Subsequently, larger and larger entangled atoms and anti-atoms are synchronously formed as more and more orbital electrons and positrons get entangled with the entangled nuclei and anti-nuclei. The spins of particles and anti-particles change synchronously due to the superposition of spin states. Thus, spin angular momentum is conserved jointly as well as periodically in atoms and anti-atoms. Like nuclei and anti-nuclei, each atom and anti-atom will have two entangled states. The two entangled states of the hydrogen and anti-hydrogen atoms will be:

$$|\psi_{1H}\bar{\psi}_{1H}\rangle_{1A} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (|\uparrow_p\downarrow_{\bar{p}}\rangle_1 |\downarrow_e\uparrow_{\bar{e}}\rangle_2 + |\downarrow_p\uparrow_{\bar{p}}\rangle_2 |\uparrow_e\downarrow_{\bar{e}}\rangle_1)$$

$$|\psi_{1H}\bar{\psi}_{1H}\rangle_{2A} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (|\uparrow_p\downarrow_{\bar{p}}\rangle_1 |\uparrow_e\uparrow_{\bar{e}}\rangle_1 + |\downarrow_p\uparrow_{\bar{p}}\rangle_2 |\downarrow_e\downarrow_{\bar{e}}\rangle_2)$$

For the same reason, multiple pairs of electrons and positrons can be indirectly entangled through protons, anti-neutrons, anti-protons, and neutrons. Two electron-positron pairs can form a pair of entangled states:

$$|e_2\bar{e}_2\rangle_1 = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (|\uparrow_e\downarrow_{\bar{e}}\rangle_1 |\downarrow_e\uparrow_{\bar{e}}\rangle_2 + |\downarrow_e\uparrow_{\bar{e}}\rangle_2 |\uparrow_e\downarrow_{\bar{e}}\rangle_2)$$

$$= \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (|\uparrow_e\downarrow_e\rangle_1 |\downarrow_{\bar{e}}\uparrow_{\bar{e}}\rangle_2 + |\downarrow_e\uparrow_e\rangle_2 |\uparrow_{\bar{e}}\downarrow_{\bar{e}}\rangle_1)$$

$$|e_2\bar{e}_2\rangle_2 = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (|\uparrow_e\uparrow_{\bar{e}}\rangle_1 |\downarrow_e\downarrow_{\bar{e}}\rangle_2 + |\downarrow_e\downarrow_{\bar{e}}\rangle_2 |\uparrow_e\uparrow_{\bar{e}}\rangle_1)$$

$$= \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (|\uparrow_e\downarrow_e\rangle_1 |\uparrow_{\bar{e}}\downarrow_{\bar{e}}\rangle_1 + |\downarrow_e\uparrow_e\rangle_2 |\downarrow_{\bar{e}}\uparrow_{\bar{e}}\rangle_2)$$

Note that in an atomic orbital, the spins of two electrons/positrons will be opposite and entangled. Four electron-positron pairs form a pair of entangled states :

$$|e_4\bar{e}_4\rangle_1 = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (|e_2\bar{e}_2\rangle_1 |e_2\bar{e}_2\rangle_1 + |e_2\bar{e}_2\rangle_2 |e_2\bar{e}_2\rangle_2)$$

$$|e_4\bar{e}_4\rangle_2 = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (|e_2\bar{e}_2\rangle_1 |e_2\bar{e}_2\rangle_2 + |e_2\bar{e}_2\rangle_2 |e_2\bar{e}_2\rangle_1)$$

A pair of higher entangled electron-positron states can be formed on the platform of lower entangled electron-positron states:

$$|e_n\bar{e}_n\rangle_1 = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (|e_m\bar{e}_m\rangle_1 |e_m\bar{e}_m\rangle_1 + |e_m\bar{e}_m\rangle_2 |e_m\bar{e}_m\rangle_2)$$

$$|e_n \bar{e}_n\rangle_2 = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (|e_m \bar{e}_m\rangle_1 |e_m \bar{e}_m\rangle_2 + |e_m \bar{e}_m\rangle_2 |e_m \bar{e}_m\rangle_1) \text{ where } n > m.$$

A pair of entangled atomic states can form from a nucleus–anti-nucleus pair together with multiple electron–positron pairs. Below are two entangled states for a helium / anti-helium atom pair.

$$|\psi_{4He} \bar{\psi}_{4He}\rangle_{1A} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (|\psi_{4He} \bar{\psi}_{4He}\rangle_1 |e_2 \bar{e}_2\rangle_2 + |\psi_{4He} \bar{\psi}_{4He}\rangle_2 |e_2 \bar{e}_2\rangle_1)$$

$$|\psi_{4He} \bar{\psi}_{4He}\rangle_{2A} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (|\psi_{4He} \bar{\psi}_{4He}\rangle_1 |e_2 \bar{e}_2\rangle_2 + |\psi_{4He} \bar{\psi}_{4He}\rangle_2 |e_2 \bar{e}_2\rangle_1)$$

Likewise, two entangled states of oxygen and anti-oxygen atoms can form:

$$|\psi_{16O} \bar{\psi}_{16O}\rangle_{1A} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (|\psi_{16O} \bar{\psi}_{16O}\rangle_1 |e_8 \bar{e}_8\rangle_2 + |\psi_{16O} \bar{\psi}_{16O}\rangle_{2A} |e_8 \bar{e}_8\rangle_1)$$

$$|\psi_{16O} \bar{\psi}_{16O}\rangle_{2A} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (|\psi_{16O} \bar{\psi}_{16O}\rangle_{1A} |e_8 \bar{e}_8\rangle_1 + |\psi_{16O} \bar{\psi}_{16O}\rangle_{2A} |e_8 \bar{e}_8\rangle_2)$$

Similarly, through quantum chemical synthesis, entangled molecules and anti-molecules are formed after the formation of entangled atoms and anti-atoms. Polyatomic molecules and anti-molecules become entangled when orbital electrons and positrons become entangled with the entangled atoms and anti-atoms. Entangled polyatomic molecules and anti-molecules are formed by the action of the attractive QS force acting between the opposite spin states of orbital electrons/positrons of two or more atoms/anti-atoms, and the repulsive QC force acting between orbital electrons/positrons of two or more atoms/anti-atoms, wherein angular momentum is jointly as well as periodically conserved. Chemical bonds are quantum bonds. Like entangled atoms and anti-atoms, entangled molecules and anti-molecules will have two entangled states. The following two entangled states of hydrogen and anti-hydrogen, and oxygen and anti-oxygen molecules will form :

$$|\psi_{H_2} \bar{\psi}_{H_2}\rangle_{1M} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (|\psi_{H_1} \bar{\psi}_{H_1}\rangle_{1A} |\psi_{H_1} \bar{\psi}_{H_1}\rangle_{2A} + |\psi_{H_1} \bar{\psi}_{H_1}\rangle_{2A} |\psi_{H_1} \bar{\psi}_{H_1}\rangle_{1A})$$

$$|\psi_{H_2} \bar{\psi}_{H_2}\rangle_{2M} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (|\psi_{H_1} \bar{\psi}_{H_1}\rangle_{1A} |\psi_{H_1} \bar{\psi}_{H_1}\rangle_{1A} + |\psi_{H_1} \bar{\psi}_{H_1}\rangle_{2A} |\psi_{H_1} \bar{\psi}_{H_1}\rangle_{2A})$$

$$|\psi_{O_2} \bar{\psi}_{O_2}\rangle_{1M} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (|\psi_{16O} \bar{\psi}_{16O}\rangle_{1A} |\psi_{16O} \bar{\psi}_{16O}\rangle_{2A} + |\psi_{16O} \bar{\psi}_{16O}\rangle_{2A} |\psi_{16O} \bar{\psi}_{16O}\rangle_{1A})$$

$$|\psi_{O_2} \bar{\psi}_{O_2}\rangle_{2M} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (|\psi_{16O} \bar{\psi}_{16O}\rangle_{1A} |\psi_{16O} \bar{\psi}_{16O}\rangle_{2A} + |\psi_{16O} \bar{\psi}_{16O}\rangle_{2A} |\psi_{16O} \bar{\psi}_{16O}\rangle_{1A})$$

Similarly, entangled state of compound is also formed.

$$|\psi_{CO_2} \bar{\psi}_{CO_2}\rangle_{1M} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (|\psi_C \bar{\psi}_C\rangle_{1M} |\psi_{O_2} \bar{\psi}_{O_2}\rangle_{2M} + |\psi_C \bar{\psi}_C\rangle_{2M} |\psi_{O_2} \bar{\psi}_{O_2}\rangle_{1M})$$

$$|\psi_{CO_2} \bar{\psi}_{CO_2}\rangle_{2M} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (|\psi_C \bar{\psi}_C\rangle_{1M} |\psi_{O_2} \bar{\psi}_{O_2}\rangle_{2M} + |\psi_C \bar{\psi}_C\rangle_{2M} |\psi_{O_2} \bar{\psi}_{O_2}\rangle_{1M})$$

In the same way, two entangled states of matter and anti-matter polymers will also form. In molecules and anti-molecules, spin angular momentum is conserved both jointly and periodically. Similar to the synchronous formation of entangled matter and anti-matter nuclei, the formation of matter and anti-matter atoms or molecules is possible due to free entangled particles and anti-particles. Accordingly, the spin polarization of neutrons, protons, electrons, anti-neutrons, anti-protons, and positrons is synchronized. The largest entangled pair of a molecule and an anti-molecule constitutes the largest synchronized system. Molecules and anti-molecules that have already been produced synchronously can also be produced asynchronously, thereby becoming entangled with the synchronously produced molecules and anti-molecules. Molecules and anti-molecules experience QS and QC forces due to

entanglement and become stable as a result of these two forces. To comply with unitary evolution, multiple copies are produced. Entanglement provides protection to ensembles of nuclei, atoms, and molecules against noise.

Quantum jumps between energy states can be better understood if we consider that the excited energy states of a nucleus, atom, or molecule are entangled with the excited energy states of the corresponding anti-nucleus, anti-atom, or anti-molecule. Identical atoms or molecules are always found in bulk in nature in close proximity, as the quantum force follows a $1/R^2$ dependence. The survival of DNA over billions of years can be better understood in the light of unitarity and entanglement. Molecules synthetically produced on Earth are direct product states and cannot be guaranteed to be permanently stable. However, there is a non-zero probability that they are also entangled states that were naturally and synchronously produced on other planets, moons, asteroids and comets.

18. Quantum Forces: To ensure the separation of neutron and anti-neutron from a qtom, P_s should be greater than P_m . To ensure the annihilation of electron-positron pair, P_s should be greater than P_c . Two electrons can occupy 1s orbital with opposite spins. To ensure the formation of 1 S orbital, the P_s of attractive QS must be greater than the P_c of the repulsive QC force.

Number of particles associated is proportional to the charges. $Q \propto N_Q$; $q \propto N_q$. $F_c \sim N_Q \cdot N_q \cdot P_c \cdot P_{en} = \frac{N_Q N_q}{N_R^2} P_c \equiv K \frac{Q, q}{R^2}$. Similarly QS force can be expressed as $F_s \sim N_S \cdot N_s \cdot P_s \cdot P_{en} = \frac{N_S N_s}{N_R^2} P_s \equiv K \frac{S, s}{R^2}$ where the number of particles manifesting spin is proportional to the spin strength: $S \propto N_S$; $s \propto N_s$. This force has already manifested as the magnetic force, which also has a $1/R^2$ nature.

To assess P_s , let us consider tritium, which emits a beta particle due to the repulsive QS force. For instability of tritium, $F_s \approx 1$. Since $N_S = 1, N_s = 1, N_R = 1$, then $P_s \approx 1$. To assess P_c , let us consider an alpha particle, which is emitted when repulsive QC force just overcomes the attractive QS force. For the instability of alpha emitter, $F_c \approx 1$. Consider an alpha emitter ${}^{209}_{81}Bi$. Almost 81 protons required to overcome the attractive QS force. When $F_c \approx 1, N_Q = 2, N_q = 79$ and $N_R \approx 1$, then $P_c \approx 0.01$.

Let us calculate force-score of attractive QC force experienced by the electron of a stable hydrogen atom. Putting $N_Q = 1, N_q = 1$ and $N_R \approx 1000$ $P_c \approx 0.01$ in the formula we get $F_c = 10^{-8}$. It implies that approximately after 10^8 attempts stable hydrogen atom formation is possible. We can write $F_c \cdot r \approx m \omega^2 \cdot r \equiv N_m \cdot \frac{4\pi^2}{N_T^2} \cdot N_R$. Using the formula and substituting the value of F_c , we get $N_T \approx 10^6$. The orbital time period is then $T = N_T \cdot \nabla t \approx 10^{-16}$ s. The velocity of electron in the 1s orbit is $v = \frac{2\pi N_R \nabla x}{N_T \nabla t} \approx 10^6$ m/s. This is reasonably in agreement with the known velocity of the 1s electron of hydrogen atom: $v \approx 2.19 \times 10^6$ m/s. In our assessment, $P_s \approx 1, P_m \approx 10^{-38}$. and $P_c \approx 0.01$. Adding the three values, we get $P_s + P_c + P_m \approx 1$. These probabilities are close to the relative strengths of gravitational force and

electromagnetic forces in comparison with the strong nuclear force. The existence of QS force is also partly manifested in Pauli exclusion principle.

19. Quantum Magnetic Force : The establishment of direction within the accumulated matter and antimatter is crucial for the evolution of the universe. Two electrons can become entangled during the formation of an atom and an anti-atom. The singlet and triplet entangled states can form with the unpaired electrons of two distant atoms with equal probability.

$$|\psi_1\rangle = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(|\uparrow_e \downarrow_e\rangle + |\downarrow_e \uparrow_e\rangle)$$

$$|\psi_2\rangle = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(|\uparrow_e \uparrow_e\rangle + |\downarrow_e \downarrow_e\rangle)$$

With the accumulation of atoms, two entangled states, $|\psi_1\rangle$ and $|\psi_2\rangle$, will be probabilistically distributed in space. This probabilistic distribution will not be uniform and can change with time. There are two possible forms of non-uniform distributions. 1. In opposite regions, $|\psi_1\rangle$ dominates and in same region $|\psi_2\rangle$ dominates. 2. In opposite regions $|\psi_2\rangle$ dominates, and in same region $|\psi_1\rangle$ dominates. In first possibility, the opposite regions (or poles) of the accumulated matter will attract each other, since $|\psi_1\rangle$ states are distributed across opposite poles and the electrons in those poles will experience attractive QS force. On the other hand, similar poles will repel each other, since $|\psi_2\rangle$ states are distributed across similar poles and the electrons there will experience a repulsive QS force.

Over time, the distribution may shift towards the second possibility. In this case, the opposite poles of the accumulated matter will repel each other, as $|\psi_2\rangle$ states dominate across opposite poles and the electrons there will experience a repulsive QS force. Meanwhile, similar pole will attract each other, since $|\psi_1\rangle$ states dominate across similar poles and their electrons will experience an attractive QS force. Due to this asymmetric, non-uniform, and time-varying distribution, a new kind of force—magnetic force—will evolve, and magnetic poles will flip periodically. For similar reasons, magnetism will arise in anti-matter structures. The biggest structures of matter and anti-matter will be the biggest magnets. Quantum magnetic force arises due to QS force. It has been observed that stars, planets, galaxies, and clusters of galaxies exhibit magnetism, and the magnetic poles of the Earth and the Sun flip during evolution.

20. Quantum Electromagnetic Force : $|\psi_1\rangle$ and $|\psi_2\rangle$ are probabilistically distributed in the matter and anti-matter structure. The question is, what will happen if the distribution is disturbed? The distribution can be locally disturbed by displacing a magnet or electrons deterministically in any direction. That is, the probabilistic distribution can be deterministically disturbed. The probabilistic evolution of the universe implies that deterministic disturbance of distribution can be nullified. Out of the three fundamental quantum forces, the QS force is directional. This suggests that the QS force may arise to nullify the disturbance. The entangled state of the proton and electron may be described in the following way:

$$|\psi_{1x}\rangle = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(|+x\rangle | -x\rangle + | -x\rangle | +x\rangle),$$

$$|\psi_{2x}\rangle = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(|+x\rangle | +x\rangle + | -x\rangle | -x\rangle),$$

The spin orientation of entangled proton and electron can jump to any of the three entangled states, generating a QS force that acts to nullify the disturbance. This process can be illustrated through the following three well-known cases.

Case 1. Suppose current flows in + or -y direction in a current carrying conductor. This implies that the global distribution of $|\psi_1\rangle$ and $|\psi_2\rangle$ is locally disturbed along + or - x direction. Now, let us place another current-carrying conductor parallel to the first one. The free electrons of the two conductors share some entangled states, and they can jump to $|\psi_{1x}\rangle$ or $|\psi_{2x}\rangle$. As a result, the two conductors can experience either an attractive or a repulsive QS force. In this way, the disturbance will be instantaneously nullified.

Case 2. Suppose a bar magnet is moving towards a circular coil, where the axis of the magnet is in the \mathbf{z} direction and the coil lies in the \mathbf{xy} plane. As soon as the magnet starts moving, the distributions $|\psi_1\rangle$ and $|\psi_2\rangle$ are locally disturbed. The circular coil and the bar magnet share some entangled electrons, which can jump to $|\psi_{2x}\rangle$ and $|\psi_{2y}\rangle$. Thus, at two opposite points in the circular coil, the electrons will experience equal and opposite repulsive QS forces. As a result, the electrons will rotate in the circular loop in the \mathbf{xy} plane. Hence, the disturbance along the \mathbf{z} direction will be instantaneously nullified.

Case 3. Suppose an electron is moving along x-axis and approaching the gap between north pole and south magnetic poles placed in the xy plane. Here, the distributions $|\psi_1\rangle$ and $|\psi_2\rangle$ are locally disturbed along x-direction. The magnetic poles and the electron beam share some entangled electrons, which can jump to $|\psi_{2x}\rangle$ and $|\psi_{2y}\rangle$. Due to repulsive QS force, the electrons will deviate in the +z or -z direction. Thus, the disturbance will be instantaneously nullified.

The quantum electromagnetic force is another manifestation of QS force, which is arising to preserve quantum evolution of the universe.

21. Instantaneous Communication : Through entangled circuits, information reaches arbitrarily distant locations instantaneously. Enormous amounts of bio-information instantaneously propagate through entangled matter and anti-matter DNA/RNA circuits. However, information moving through entangled circuits is essentially probabilistic in nature. For communication, information needs to be sent deterministically. Using entanglement, definite information can be sent instantaneously since entangled particles can serve as a receiving center in advance. Although particles cannot exceed the limiting speed, information can. Instantaneous communication is possible by generating a repulsive QS force. The above three simple experimental setups can be used to verify this possibility—that is, the force can carry a bit of information. However, the quantum force is $1/R^2$ in nature, so it will be too weak to decode bit values for long-distance instantaneous communication. The QS force decreases with distance because the probability of entanglement decreases with the square of the distance between entangled particles.

This is true for naturally occurring entanglement. But if entanglement is locally created and distributed over large distances, the quantum force will not decrease with distance. It is not theoretically impossible to create entangled magnets and entangled conductors. Therefore, instantaneous communication over large distances is, in principle, possible.

Although the presented model/theory is consistent with the vast amount of experimental data, further experimental verifications can strengthen it. But the problem is, experimental data can be misinterpreted in favor of a theory, and such misinterpretation can propagate over a long period of time. This is also true for the presented model, even it is further experimentally verified. To overcome this problem, logical consistency of the theory can be checked. The presented model is open to all for a Logical Consistency Test (LCT). The following points may be taken into consideration for LCT.

- 1.** The quantum universe requires three-dimensional space, three fundamental forces, three fundamental physical quantities, and three matter/anti-matter particles. Quantum mechanics is also built on three foundational principles: discreteness/probabilistic structure, indistinguishability and entanglement. Three dimensional evolution minimizes the complexity of evolution and thereby perhaps minimizes the energy cost of evolution.
- 2.** Information in randomly created qatoms cannot be destroyed because it is fundamentally quantum in nature. If this information is not lost, one can expect that randomly created qatoms should generate random numbers in space. It has been observed that random numbers can indeed be extracted from space, which can be used to generate completely secure online keys [27].
- 3.** If the universe expands linearly with time, it can be expected that all computational problems must be solved within linear time. Otherwise information in the universe cannot be recovered. We have pointed out [28] that all computational problems can be solved in linear time.
- 4.** It can be expected that in a quantum universe, secure or insecure completely quantum communication with aliens will be possible, with or without using entangled states. It has been pointed out that secure or insecure quantum communication with aliens is possible following alternative quantum coding [28]. Alternative quantum coding is also compatible with the quantum model of the evolution of the universe.
- 5.** If the universe evolves quantum mechanically then it can be expected that species should evolve quantum mechanically. We have developed a model on quantum evolution of species [29]. These two models are complementary to each other.

In conclusion, it appears that the Supreme Power of quantum mechanics is manifested through the evolution of the universe, and quantum mechanics is $\sim 10^{120}$ times more accurate in comparison with relativity and field theory. Quantum mechanics may be considered a Theory of Everything [8-12].

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Table-1

Synthesis of stable entangled nuclei and anti-nuclei

1. ${}^1_1\text{H} + \text{n} \rightarrow {}^2_1\text{D} \leftrightarrow {}^2_1\bar{\text{D}} \leftarrow \bar{\text{n}} + {}^1_1\bar{\text{H}}$
2. ${}^2_1\text{D} + {}^1_1\text{H} \rightarrow {}^3_2\text{He} \leftrightarrow {}^3_2\bar{\text{He}} \leftarrow {}^1_1\bar{\text{H}} + {}^2_1\bar{\text{D}}$
3. ${}^2_1\text{D} + {}^2_1\text{D} \rightarrow {}^4_2\text{He} \leftrightarrow {}^4_2\bar{\text{He}} \leftarrow {}^2_1\bar{\text{D}} + {}^2_1\bar{\text{D}}$
4. ${}^4_2\text{He} + {}^2_1\text{D} \rightarrow {}^6_3\text{Li} \leftrightarrow {}^6_3\bar{\text{Li}} \leftarrow {}^4_2\bar{\text{He}} + {}^2_1\bar{\text{D}}$
5. ${}^3_2\text{He} + {}^2_2\text{He} \rightarrow {}^4_4\text{Be} + \text{e} \rightarrow {}^7_3\text{Li} \leftrightarrow {}^7_3\bar{\text{Li}} \leftarrow {}^4_4\bar{\text{Be}} + \bar{\text{e}} \leftarrow {}^3_2\bar{\text{He}} + {}^4_2\bar{\text{He}}$
6. ${}^7_3\text{Li} + {}^2_1\text{D} \rightarrow {}^9_4\text{Be} \leftrightarrow {}^9_4\bar{\text{Be}} \leftarrow {}^7_3\bar{\text{Li}} + {}^2_1\bar{\text{D}}$
7. ${}^7_3\text{Li} + {}^3_2\text{He} \rightarrow {}^{10}_5\text{B} \leftrightarrow {}^{10}_5\bar{\text{B}} \leftarrow {}^7_3\bar{\text{Li}} + {}^3_2\bar{\text{He}}$
8. ${}^4_2\text{He} + {}^7_3\text{Li} \rightarrow {}^{11}_5\text{B} \leftrightarrow {}^{11}_5\bar{\text{B}} \leftarrow {}^4_2\bar{\text{He}} + {}^7_3\bar{\text{Li}}$
9. ${}^{10}_5\text{B} + {}^2_1\text{D} \rightarrow {}^{12}_6\text{C} \leftrightarrow {}^{12}_6\bar{\text{C}} \leftarrow {}^{10}_5\bar{\text{B}} + {}^2_1\bar{\text{D}}$
10. ${}^{11}_5\text{B} + {}^2_1\text{D} \rightarrow {}^{13}_6\text{C} \leftrightarrow {}^{13}_6\bar{\text{C}} \leftarrow {}^{11}_5\bar{\text{B}} + {}^2_1\bar{\text{D}}$
11. ${}^{10}_5\text{B} + {}^4_2\text{He} \rightarrow {}^{14}_7\text{N} \leftrightarrow {}^{14}_7\bar{\text{N}} \leftarrow {}^{10}_5\bar{\text{B}} + {}^4_2\bar{\text{He}}$
12. ${}^{11}_5\text{B} + {}^4_2\text{He} \rightarrow {}^{15}_7\text{N} \leftrightarrow {}^{15}_7\bar{\text{N}} \leftarrow {}^{11}_5\bar{\text{B}} + {}^4_2\bar{\text{He}}$
13. ${}^{12}_6\text{C} + {}^4_2\text{He} \rightarrow {}^{16}_8\text{O} \leftrightarrow {}^{16}_8\bar{\text{O}} \leftarrow {}^{12}_6\bar{\text{C}} + {}^4_2\bar{\text{He}}$
14. ${}^{13}_6\text{C} + {}^4_2\text{He} \rightarrow {}^{17}_8\text{O} \leftrightarrow {}^{17}_8\bar{\text{O}} \leftarrow {}^{13}_6\bar{\text{C}} + {}^4_2\bar{\text{He}}$
15. ${}^{11}_5\text{B} + {}^7_3\text{Li} \rightarrow {}^{18}_8\text{O} \leftrightarrow {}^{18}_8\bar{\text{O}} \leftarrow {}^{11}_5\bar{\text{B}} + {}^7_3\bar{\text{Li}}$
16. ${}^{17}_8\text{O} + {}^2_1\text{D} \rightarrow {}^{19}_9\text{F} \leftrightarrow {}^{19}_9\bar{\text{F}} \leftarrow {}^{17}_8\bar{\text{O}} + {}^2_1\bar{\text{D}}$
17. ${}^{16}_8\text{O} + {}^4_2\text{He} \rightarrow {}^{20}_{10}\text{Ne} \leftrightarrow {}^{20}_{10}\bar{\text{Ne}} \leftarrow {}^{16}_8\bar{\text{O}} + {}^4_2\bar{\text{He}}$
18. ${}^{12}_6\text{C} + {}^9_4\text{Be} \rightarrow {}^{21}_{10}\text{Ne} \leftrightarrow {}^{21}_{10}\bar{\text{Ne}} \leftarrow {}^{12}_6\bar{\text{C}} + {}^9_4\bar{\text{Be}}$
19. ${}^{13}_6\text{C} + {}^9_4\text{Be} \rightarrow {}^{22}_{10}\text{Ne} \leftrightarrow {}^{22}_{10}\bar{\text{Ne}} \leftarrow {}^{13}_6\bar{\text{C}} + {}^9_4\bar{\text{Be}}$
20. ${}^{12}_6\text{C} + {}^{11}_5\text{B} \rightarrow {}^{23}_{11}\text{Na} \leftrightarrow {}^{23}_{11}\bar{\text{Na}} \leftarrow {}^{12}_6\bar{\text{C}} + {}^{11}_5\bar{\text{B}}$
21. ${}^{20}_{10}\text{Ne} + {}^4_2\text{He} \rightarrow {}^{24}_{12}\text{Mg} \leftrightarrow {}^{24}_{12}\bar{\text{Mg}} \leftarrow {}^{20}_{10}\bar{\text{Ne}} + {}^4_2\bar{\text{He}}$
22. ${}^{21}_{10}\text{Ne} + {}^4_2\text{He} \rightarrow {}^{25}_{12}\text{Mg} \leftrightarrow {}^{25}_{12}\bar{\text{Mg}} \leftarrow {}^{21}_{10}\bar{\text{Ne}} + {}^4_2\bar{\text{He}}$
23. ${}^{19}_9\text{F} + {}^7_3\text{Li} \rightarrow {}^{26}_{12}\text{Mg} \leftrightarrow {}^{26}_{12}\bar{\text{Mg}} \leftarrow {}^{19}_9\bar{\text{F}} + {}^7_3\bar{\text{Li}}$
24. ${}^{20}_{10}\text{Ne} + {}^7_3\text{Li} \rightarrow {}^{27}_{13}\text{Al} \leftrightarrow {}^{27}_{13}\bar{\text{Al}} \leftarrow {}^{20}_{10}\bar{\text{Ne}} + {}^7_3\bar{\text{Li}}$
25. ${}^{24}_{12}\text{Mg} + {}^4_2\text{He} \rightarrow {}^{28}_{14}\text{Si} \leftrightarrow {}^{28}_{14}\bar{\text{Si}} \leftarrow {}^{24}_{12}\bar{\text{Mg}} + {}^4_2\bar{\text{He}}$
26. ${}^{25}_{12}\text{Mg} + {}^4_2\text{He} \rightarrow {}^{29}_{14}\text{Si} \leftrightarrow {}^{29}_{14}\bar{\text{Si}} \leftarrow {}^{25}_{12}\bar{\text{Mg}} + {}^4_2\bar{\text{He}}$
27. ${}^{26}_{12}\text{Mg} + {}^4_2\text{He} \rightarrow {}^{30}_{14}\text{Si} \leftrightarrow {}^{30}_{14}\bar{\text{Si}} \leftarrow {}^{26}_{12}\bar{\text{Mg}} + {}^4_2\bar{\text{He}}$
28. ${}^{24}_{12}\text{Mg} + {}^7_3\text{Li} \rightarrow {}^{31}_{15}\text{P} \leftrightarrow {}^{31}_{15}\bar{\text{P}} \leftarrow {}^{24}_{12}\bar{\text{Mg}} + {}^7_3\bar{\text{Li}}$
29. ${}^{28}_{14}\text{Si} + {}^4_2\text{He} \rightarrow {}^{32}_{16}\text{S} \leftrightarrow {}^{32}_{16}\bar{\text{S}} \leftarrow {}^{28}_{14}\bar{\text{Si}} + {}^4_2\bar{\text{He}}$
30. ${}^{21}_{10}\text{Ne} + {}^{12}_6\text{C} \rightarrow {}^{33}_{16}\text{S} \leftrightarrow {}^{33}_{16}\bar{\text{S}} \leftarrow {}^{21}_{10}\bar{\text{Ne}} + {}^{12}_6\bar{\text{C}}$
31. ${}^{27}_{13}\text{Al} + {}^7_3\text{Li} \rightarrow {}^{34}_{16}\text{S} \leftrightarrow {}^{34}_{16}\bar{\text{S}} \leftarrow {}^{27}_{13}\bar{\text{Al}} + {}^7_3\bar{\text{Li}}$
32. ${}^{25}_{12}\text{Mg} + {}^{11}_5\text{B} \rightarrow {}^{36}_{17}\text{Cl} + \text{e} \rightarrow {}^{36}_{16}\text{S} \leftrightarrow {}^{36}_{16}\bar{\text{S}} \leftarrow {}^{36}_{17}\bar{\text{Cl}} + \bar{\text{e}} \leftarrow {}^{25}_{12}\bar{\text{Mg}} + {}^{11}_5\bar{\text{B}}$
33. ${}^{31}_{15}\text{P} + {}^4_2\text{He} \rightarrow {}^{35}_{17}\text{Cl} \leftrightarrow {}^{35}_{17}\bar{\text{Cl}} \leftarrow {}^{31}_{15}\bar{\text{P}} + {}^4_2\bar{\text{He}}$
34. ${}^{36}_{16}\text{S} + {}^2_1\text{D} \rightarrow {}^{37}_{17}\text{Cl} \leftrightarrow {}^{37}_{17}\bar{\text{Cl}} \leftarrow {}^{36}_{16}\bar{\text{S}} + {}^2_1\bar{\text{D}}$
35. ${}^{24}_{12}\text{Mg} + {}^{12}_6\text{C} \rightarrow {}^{36}_{18}\text{Ar} \leftrightarrow {}^{36}_{18}\bar{\text{Ar}} \leftarrow {}^{24}_{12}\bar{\text{Mg}} + {}^{12}_6\bar{\text{C}}$
36. ${}^{31}_{15}\text{P} + {}^7_3\text{Li} \rightarrow {}^{38}_{18}\text{Ar} \leftrightarrow {}^{38}_{18}\bar{\text{Ar}} \leftarrow {}^{31}_{15}\bar{\text{P}} + {}^7_3\bar{\text{Li}}$
37. ${}^{36}_{16}\text{S} + {}^4_2\text{He} \rightarrow {}^{40}_{18}\text{Ar} \leftrightarrow {}^{40}_{18}\bar{\text{Ar}} \leftarrow {}^{36}_{16}\bar{\text{S}} + {}^4_2\bar{\text{He}}$
38. ${}^{35}_{17}\text{Cl} + {}^4_2\text{He} \rightarrow {}^{39}_{19}\text{K} \leftrightarrow {}^{39}_{19}\bar{\text{K}} \leftarrow {}^{35}_{17}\bar{\text{Cl}} + {}^4_2\bar{\text{He}}$

39. ${}_{17}^{37}\text{Cl} + {}_2^4\text{He} \rightarrow {}_{19}^{41}\text{K} \leftrightarrow {}_{19}^{41}\overline{\text{K}} \leftarrow {}_{17}^{37}\overline{\text{Cl}} + {}_2^4\overline{\text{He}}$
40. ${}_{18}^{36}\text{Ar} + {}_2^4\text{He} \rightarrow {}_{20}^{40}\text{Ca} \leftrightarrow {}_{20}^{40}\overline{\text{Ca}} \leftarrow {}_{18}^{36}\overline{\text{Ar}} + {}_2^4\overline{\text{He}}$
41. ${}_{18}^{38}\text{Ar} + {}_2^4\text{He} \rightarrow {}_{20}^{42}\text{Ca} \leftrightarrow {}_{20}^{42}\overline{\text{Ca}} \leftarrow {}_{18}^{38}\overline{\text{Ar}} + {}_2^4\overline{\text{He}}$
42. ${}_{19}^{41}\text{K} + {}_1^2\text{D} \rightarrow {}_{20}^{43}\text{Ca} \leftrightarrow {}_{20}^{43}\overline{\text{Ca}} \leftarrow {}_{19}^{41}\overline{\text{K}} + {}_1^2\overline{\text{D}}$
43. ${}_{17}^{37}\text{Cl} + {}_3^7\text{Li} \rightarrow {}_{20}^{44}\text{Ca} \leftrightarrow {}_{20}^{44}\overline{\text{Ca}} \leftarrow {}_{17}^{37}\overline{\text{Cl}} + {}_3^7\overline{\text{Li}}$
44. ${}_{17}^{37}\text{Cl} + {}_4^9\text{B} \rightarrow {}_{21}^{46}\text{Sc} + e \rightarrow {}_{20}^{46}\text{Ca} \leftrightarrow {}_{20}^{46}\overline{\text{Ca}} \leftarrow {}_{21}^{46}\overline{\text{Sc}} + \bar{e} \leftarrow {}_{17}^{37}\overline{\text{Cl}} + {}_4^9\overline{\text{B}}$
45. ${}_{18}^{38}\text{Ar} + {}_3^7\text{Li} \rightarrow {}_{21}^{45}\text{Sc} \leftrightarrow {}_{21}^{45}\overline{\text{Sc}} \leftarrow {}_{18}^{38}\overline{\text{Ar}} + {}_3^7\overline{\text{Li}}$
46. ${}_{20}^{42}\text{Ca} + {}_2^4\text{He} \rightarrow {}_{22}^{46}\text{Ti} \leftrightarrow {}_{22}^{46}\overline{\text{Ti}} \leftarrow {}_{20}^{42}\overline{\text{Ca}} + {}_2^4\overline{\text{He}}$
47. ${}_{21}^{45}\text{Sc} + {}_1^2\text{D} \rightarrow {}_{22}^{47}\text{Ti} \leftrightarrow {}_{22}^{47}\overline{\text{Ti}} \leftarrow {}_{21}^{45}\overline{\text{Sc}} + {}_1^2\overline{\text{D}}$
48. ${}_{20}^{44}\text{Ca} + {}_2^4\text{He} \rightarrow {}_{22}^{48}\text{Ti} \leftrightarrow {}_{22}^{48}\overline{\text{Ti}} \leftarrow {}_{20}^{44}\overline{\text{Ca}} + {}_2^4\overline{\text{He}}$
49. ${}_{18}^{40}\text{Ar} + {}_4^9\text{Be} \rightarrow {}_{22}^{49}\text{Ti} \leftrightarrow {}_{22}^{49}\overline{\text{Ti}} \leftarrow {}_{18}^{40}\overline{\text{Ar}} + {}_4^9\overline{\text{Be}}$
50. ${}_{22}^{48}\text{Ti} + {}_1^2\text{D} \rightarrow {}_{23}^{50}\text{V} + \bar{e} \rightarrow {}_{22}^{50}\text{Ti} \leftrightarrow {}_{22}^{50}\overline{\text{Ti}} \leftarrow {}_{23}^{50}\overline{\text{V}} + e \leftarrow {}_{22}^{48}\overline{\text{Ti}} + {}_1^2\overline{\text{D}}^{**}$
51. ${}_{22}^{49}\text{Ti} + {}_1^2\text{D} \rightarrow {}_{23}^{51}\text{V} \leftrightarrow {}_{23}^{51}\overline{\text{V}} \leftarrow {}_{22}^{49}\overline{\text{Ti}} + {}_1^2\overline{\text{D}}$
52. ${}_{22}^{46}\text{Ti} + {}_2^4\text{He} \rightarrow {}_{24}^{50}\text{Cr} \leftrightarrow {}_{24}^{50}\overline{\text{Cr}} \leftarrow {}_{22}^{46}\overline{\text{Ti}} + {}_2^4\overline{\text{He}}$
53. ${}_{21}^{45}\text{Sc} + {}_3^7\text{Li} \rightarrow {}_{24}^{52}\text{Cr} \leftrightarrow {}_{24}^{52}\overline{\text{Cr}} \leftarrow {}_{21}^{45}\overline{\text{Sc}} + {}_3^7\overline{\text{Li}}$
54. ${}_{23}^{51}\text{V} + {}_1^2\text{D} \rightarrow {}_{24}^{53}\text{Cr} \leftrightarrow {}_{24}^{53}\overline{\text{Cr}} \leftarrow {}_{23}^{51}\overline{\text{V}} + {}_1^2\overline{\text{D}}$
55. ${}_{22}^{50}\text{Ti} + {}_2^4\text{He} \rightarrow {}_{24}^{54}\text{Cr} \leftrightarrow {}_{24}^{54}\overline{\text{Cr}} \leftarrow {}_{22}^{50}\overline{\text{Ti}} + {}_2^4\overline{\text{He}}$
56. ${}_{24}^{53}\text{Cr} + {}_1^2\text{D} \rightarrow {}_{25}^{55}\text{Mn} \leftrightarrow {}_{25}^{55}\overline{\text{Mn}} \leftarrow {}_{24}^{53}\overline{\text{Cr}} + {}_1^2\overline{\text{D}}$
57. ${}_{24}^{50}\text{Cr} + {}_2^4\text{He} \rightarrow {}_{26}^{54}\text{Fe} \leftrightarrow {}_{26}^{54}\overline{\text{Fe}} \leftarrow {}_{24}^{50}\overline{\text{Cr}} + {}_2^4\overline{\text{He}}$
58. ${}_{24}^{52}\text{Cr} + {}_2^4\text{He} \rightarrow {}_{26}^{56}\text{Fe} \leftrightarrow {}_{26}^{56}\overline{\text{Fe}} \leftarrow {}_{24}^{52}\overline{\text{Cr}} + {}_2^4\overline{\text{He}}$
59. ${}_{24}^{53}\text{Cr} + {}_2^4\text{He} \rightarrow {}_{26}^{57}\text{Fe} \leftrightarrow {}_{26}^{57}\overline{\text{Fe}} \leftarrow {}_{24}^{53}\overline{\text{Cr}} + {}_2^4\overline{\text{He}}$
60. ${}_{23}^{51}\text{V} + {}_3^7\text{Li} \rightarrow {}_{26}^{58}\text{Fe} \leftrightarrow {}_{26}^{58}\overline{\text{Fe}} \leftarrow {}_{23}^{51}\overline{\text{V}} + {}_3^7\overline{\text{Li}}$
61. ${}_{26}^{57}\text{Fe} + {}_1^2\text{D} \rightarrow {}_{27}^{59}\text{Co} \leftrightarrow {}_{27}^{59}\overline{\text{Co}} \leftarrow {}_{26}^{57}\overline{\text{Fe}} + {}_1^2\overline{\text{D}}$
62. ${}_{26}^{54}\text{Fe} + {}_2^4\text{He} \rightarrow {}_{28}^{58}\text{Ni} \leftrightarrow {}_{28}^{58}\overline{\text{Ni}} \leftarrow {}_{26}^{54}\overline{\text{Fe}} + {}_2^4\overline{\text{He}}$
63. ${}_{26}^{56}\text{Fe} + {}_2^4\text{He} \rightarrow {}_{28}^{60}\text{Ni} \leftrightarrow {}_{28}^{60}\overline{\text{Ni}} \leftarrow {}_{26}^{56}\overline{\text{Fe}} + {}_2^4\overline{\text{He}}$
64. ${}_{26}^{57}\text{Fe} + {}_2^4\text{He} \rightarrow {}_{28}^{61}\text{Ni} \leftrightarrow {}_{28}^{61}\overline{\text{Ni}} \leftarrow {}_{26}^{57}\overline{\text{Fe}} + {}_2^4\overline{\text{He}}$
65. ${}_{26}^{58}\text{Fe} + {}_2^4\text{He} \rightarrow {}_{28}^{62}\text{Ni} \leftrightarrow {}_{28}^{62}\overline{\text{Ni}} \leftarrow {}_{26}^{58}\overline{\text{Fe}} + {}_2^4\overline{\text{He}}$
66. ${}_{20}^{46}\text{Ca} + {}_8^{18}\text{O} \rightarrow {}_{28}^{64}\text{Ni} \leftrightarrow {}_{28}^{64}\overline{\text{Ni}} \leftarrow {}_{20}^{46}\overline{\text{Ca}} + {}_8^{18}\overline{\text{O}}$
67. ${}_{28}^{61}\text{Ni} + {}_1^2\text{D} \rightarrow {}_{29}^{63}\text{Cu} \leftrightarrow {}_{29}^{63}\overline{\text{Cu}} \leftarrow {}_{28}^{61}\overline{\text{Ni}} + {}_1^2\overline{\text{D}}$
68. ${}_{26}^{58}\text{Fe} + {}_3^7\text{Li} \rightarrow {}_{29}^{65}\text{Cu} \leftrightarrow {}_{29}^{65}\overline{\text{Cu}} \leftarrow {}_{26}^{58}\overline{\text{Fe}} + {}_3^7\overline{\text{Li}}$
69. ${}_{28}^{60}\text{Ni} + {}_2^4\text{He} \rightarrow {}_{30}^{64}\text{Zn} \leftrightarrow {}_{30}^{64}\overline{\text{Zn}} \leftarrow {}_{28}^{60}\overline{\text{Ni}} + {}_2^4\overline{\text{He}}$
70. ${}_{28}^{62}\text{Ni} + {}_2^4\text{He} \rightarrow {}_{30}^{66}\text{Zn} \leftrightarrow {}_{30}^{66}\overline{\text{Zn}} \leftarrow {}_{28}^{62}\overline{\text{Ni}} + {}_2^4\overline{\text{He}}$
71. ${}_{29}^{65}\text{Cu} + {}_1^2\text{D} \rightarrow {}_{30}^{67}\text{Zn} \leftrightarrow {}_{30}^{67}\overline{\text{Zn}} \leftarrow {}_{29}^{65}\overline{\text{Cu}} + {}_1^2\overline{\text{D}}$
72. ${}_{28}^{64}\text{Ni} + {}_2^4\text{He} \rightarrow {}_{30}^{68}\text{Zn} \leftrightarrow {}_{30}^{68}\overline{\text{Zn}} \leftarrow {}_{28}^{64}\overline{\text{Ni}} + {}_2^4\overline{\text{He}}$
73. ${}_{30}^{68}\text{Zn} + {}_1^2\text{D} \rightarrow {}_{31}^{70}\text{Ga} + e \rightarrow {}_{30}^{70}\text{Zn} \leftrightarrow {}_{30}^{70}\overline{\text{Zn}} \leftarrow {}_{31}^{70}\overline{\text{Ga}} + \bar{e} \leftarrow {}_{30}^{68}\overline{\text{Zn}} + {}_1^2\overline{\text{D}}$
74. ${}_{30}^{67}\text{Zn} + {}_1^2\text{D} \rightarrow {}_{31}^{69}\text{Ga} \leftrightarrow {}_{31}^{69}\overline{\text{Ga}} \leftarrow {}_{30}^{67}\overline{\text{Zn}} + {}_1^2\overline{\text{D}}$
75. ${}_{28}^{64}\text{Ni} + {}_3^7\text{Li} \rightarrow {}_{31}^{71}\text{Ga} \leftrightarrow {}_{31}^{71}\overline{\text{Ga}} \leftarrow {}_{28}^{64}\overline{\text{Ni}} + {}_3^7\overline{\text{Li}}$
76. ${}_{30}^{66}\text{Zn} + {}_2^4\text{He} \rightarrow {}_{32}^{70}\text{Ge} \leftrightarrow {}_{32}^{70}\overline{\text{Ge}} \leftarrow {}_{30}^{66}\overline{\text{Zn}} + {}_2^4\overline{\text{He}}$
77. ${}_{29}^{65}\text{Cu} + {}_3^7\text{Li} \rightarrow {}_{32}^{72}\text{Ge} \leftrightarrow {}_{32}^{72}\overline{\text{Ge}} \leftarrow {}_{29}^{65}\overline{\text{Cu}} + {}_3^7\overline{\text{Li}}$
78. ${}_{30}^{70}\text{Zn} + {}_2^4\text{He} \rightarrow {}_{32}^{74}\text{Ge} \leftrightarrow {}_{32}^{74}\overline{\text{Ge}} \leftarrow {}_{30}^{70}\overline{\text{Zn}} + {}_2^4\overline{\text{He}}$
79. ${}_{30}^{70}\text{Zn} + {}_2^4\text{He} \rightarrow {}_{32}^{74}\text{Ge} \leftrightarrow {}_{32}^{74}\overline{\text{Ge}} \leftarrow {}_{30}^{70}\overline{\text{Zn}} + {}_2^4\overline{\text{He}}$
80. ${}_{32}^{72}\text{Ge} + {}_2^4\text{He} \rightarrow {}_{34}^{76}\text{Se} + e \rightarrow {}_{33}^{75}\text{As} \leftrightarrow {}_{33}^{75}\overline{\text{As}} \leftarrow {}_{34}^{75}\overline{\text{Se}} + \bar{e} \leftarrow {}_{32}^{72}\overline{\text{Ge}} + {}_2^4\overline{\text{He}}$
81. ${}_{32}^{70}\text{Ge} + {}_2^4\text{He} \rightarrow {}_{34}^{74}\text{Se} \leftrightarrow {}_{34}^{74}\overline{\text{Se}} \leftarrow {}_{32}^{70}\overline{\text{Ge}} + {}_2^4\overline{\text{He}}$
82. ${}_{32}^{72}\text{Ge} + {}_2^4\text{He} \rightarrow {}_{34}^{76}\text{Se} \leftrightarrow {}_{34}^{76}\overline{\text{Se}} \leftarrow {}_{32}^{72}\overline{\text{Ge}} + {}_2^4\overline{\text{He}}$
83. ${}_{32}^{74}\text{Ge} + {}_2^4\text{He} \rightarrow {}_{34}^{78}\text{Se} \leftrightarrow {}_{34}^{78}\overline{\text{Se}} \leftarrow {}_{32}^{74}\overline{\text{Ge}} + {}_2^4\overline{\text{He}}$

218. ${}_{72}^{180}\text{Hf} + {}_2^3\text{He} \rightarrow {}_{74}^{183}\text{W} \leftrightarrow {}_{74}^{183}\overline{\text{W}} \leftarrow {}_{72}^{180}\overline{\text{Hf}} + {}_2^3\overline{\text{He}}$
219. ${}_{72}^{180}\text{Hf} + {}_2^4\text{He} \rightarrow {}_{74}^{184}\text{W} \leftrightarrow {}_{74}^{184}\overline{\text{W}} \leftarrow {}_{72}^{180}\overline{\text{Hf}} + {}_2^4\overline{\text{He}}$
220. ${}_{74}^{183}\text{W} + {}_1^2\text{D} \rightarrow {}_{75}^{186}\text{Re} + e \rightarrow {}_{74}^{186}\text{W} \leftrightarrow {}_{74}^{186}\overline{\text{W}} \leftarrow {}_{75}^{186}\overline{\text{Re}} + \bar{e} \leftarrow {}_{74}^{183}\overline{\text{W}} + {}_1^2\overline{\text{D}}$
221. ${}_{74}^{183}\text{W} + {}_1^2\text{D} \rightarrow {}_{75}^{185}\text{Re} \leftrightarrow {}_{75}^{185}\overline{\text{Re}} \leftarrow {}_{74}^{183}\overline{\text{W}} + {}_1^2\overline{\text{D}}$
222. ${}_{75}^{185}\text{Re} + {}_1^2\text{D} \rightarrow {}_{76}^{187}\text{Os} \leftrightarrow {}_{76}^{187}\overline{\text{Os}} \leftarrow {}_{75}^{185}\overline{\text{Re}} + {}_1^2\overline{\text{D}}$
223. ${}_{73}^{181}\text{Ta} + {}_3^7\text{Li} \rightarrow {}_{76}^{188}\text{Os} \leftrightarrow {}_{76}^{188}\overline{\text{Os}} \leftarrow {}_{73}^{181}\overline{\text{Ta}} + {}_3^7\overline{\text{Li}}$
224. ${}_{74}^{186}\text{W} + {}_2^3\text{He} \rightarrow {}_{76}^{189}\text{Os} \leftrightarrow {}_{76}^{189}\overline{\text{Os}} \leftarrow {}_{74}^{186}\overline{\text{W}} + {}_2^3\overline{\text{He}}$
225. ${}_{74}^{186}\text{W} + {}_2^4\text{He} \rightarrow {}_{76}^{190}\text{Os} \leftrightarrow {}_{76}^{190}\overline{\text{Os}} \leftarrow {}_{74}^{186}\overline{\text{W}} + {}_2^4\overline{\text{He}}$
226. ${}_{76}^{190}\text{Os} + {}_1^2\text{D} \rightarrow {}_{77}^{192}\text{Ir} + e \rightarrow {}_{76}^{192}\text{Os} \leftrightarrow {}_{76}^{192}\overline{\text{Os}} \leftarrow {}_{77}^{192}\overline{\text{Ir}} + \bar{e} \leftarrow {}_{76}^{190}\overline{\text{Os}} + {}_1^2\overline{\text{D}}$
227. ${}_{76}^{189}\text{Os} + {}_1^2\text{D} \rightarrow {}_{77}^{191}\text{Ir} \leftrightarrow {}_{77}^{191}\overline{\text{Ir}} \leftarrow {}_{76}^{189}\overline{\text{Os}} + {}_1^2\overline{\text{D}}$
228. ${}_{74}^{186}\text{W} + {}_3^7\text{Li} \rightarrow {}_{77}^{193}\text{Ir} \leftrightarrow {}_{77}^{193}\overline{\text{Ir}} \leftarrow {}_{74}^{186}\overline{\text{W}} + {}_3^7\overline{\text{Li}}$
229. ${}_{76}^{188}\text{Os} + {}_2^4\text{He} \rightarrow {}_{78}^{192}\text{Pt} \leftrightarrow {}_{78}^{192}\overline{\text{Pt}} \leftarrow {}_{76}^{188}\overline{\text{Os}} + {}_2^4\overline{\text{He}}$
230. ${}_{76}^{190}\text{Os} + {}_2^4\text{He} \rightarrow {}_{78}^{194}\text{Pt} \leftrightarrow {}_{78}^{194}\overline{\text{Pt}} \leftarrow {}_{76}^{190}\overline{\text{Os}} + {}_2^4\overline{\text{He}}$
231. ${}_{76}^{192}\text{Os} + {}_2^3\text{He} \rightarrow {}_{78}^{195}\text{Pt} \leftrightarrow {}_{78}^{195}\overline{\text{Pt}} \leftarrow {}_{76}^{192}\overline{\text{Os}} + {}_2^3\overline{\text{He}}$
232. ${}_{76}^{192}\text{Os} + {}_2^4\text{He} \rightarrow {}_{78}^{196}\text{Pt} \leftrightarrow {}_{78}^{196}\overline{\text{Pt}} \leftarrow {}_{76}^{192}\overline{\text{Os}} + {}_2^4\overline{\text{He}}$
233. ${}_{78}^{195}\text{Pt} + {}_1^2\text{D} \rightarrow {}_{79}^{197}\text{Au} \leftrightarrow {}_{79}^{197}\overline{\text{Au}} \leftarrow {}_{78}^{195}\overline{\text{Pt}} + {}_1^2\overline{\text{D}}$
234. ${}_{78}^{192}\text{Pt} + {}_2^4\text{He} \rightarrow {}_{80}^{196}\text{Hg} \leftrightarrow {}_{80}^{196}\overline{\text{Hg}} \leftarrow {}_{78}^{192}\overline{\text{Pt}} + {}_2^4\overline{\text{He}}$
235. ${}_{77}^{191}\text{Ir} + {}_3^7\text{Li} \rightarrow {}_{80}^{198}\text{Hg} \leftrightarrow {}_{80}^{198}\overline{\text{Hg}} \leftarrow {}_{77}^{191}\overline{\text{Ir}} + {}_3^7\overline{\text{Li}}$
236. ${}_{78}^{196}\text{Pt} + {}_2^3\text{He} \rightarrow {}_{80}^{199}\text{Hg} \leftrightarrow {}_{80}^{199}\overline{\text{Hg}} \leftarrow {}_{78}^{196}\overline{\text{Pt}} + {}_2^3\overline{\text{He}}$
237. ${}_{77}^{193}\text{Ir} + {}_3^7\text{Li} \rightarrow {}_{80}^{200}\text{Hg} \leftrightarrow {}_{80}^{200}\overline{\text{Hg}} \leftarrow {}_{77}^{193}\overline{\text{Ir}} + {}_3^7\overline{\text{Li}}$
238. ${}_{79}^{197}\text{Au} + {}_2^4\text{He} \rightarrow {}_{81}^{201}\text{Tl} + e \rightarrow {}_{80}^{201}\text{Hg} \leftrightarrow {}_{80}^{201}\overline{\text{Hg}} \leftarrow {}_{81}^{201}\overline{\text{Tl}} + \bar{e} \leftarrow {}_{79}^{197}\overline{\text{Au}} + {}_2^4\overline{\text{He}}$
239. ${}_{80}^{200}\text{Hg} + {}_1^2\text{D} \rightarrow {}_{81}^{202}\text{Tl} + e \rightarrow {}_{80}^{202}\text{Hg} \leftrightarrow {}_{80}^{202}\overline{\text{Hg}} \leftarrow {}_{81}^{202}\overline{\text{Tl}} + \bar{e} \leftarrow {}_{80}^{200}\overline{\text{Hg}} + {}_1^2\overline{\text{D}}$
240. ${}_{80}^{202}\text{Hg} + {}_1^2\text{D} \rightarrow {}_{81}^{204}\text{Tl} + e \rightarrow {}_{80}^{204}\text{Hg} \leftrightarrow {}_{80}^{204}\overline{\text{Hg}} \leftarrow {}_{81}^{204}\overline{\text{Tl}} + \bar{e} \leftarrow {}_{80}^{202}\overline{\text{Hg}} + {}_1^2\overline{\text{D}}$
241. ${}_{80}^{201}\text{Hg} + {}_1^2\text{D} \rightarrow {}_{81}^{203}\text{Tl} \leftrightarrow {}_{81}^{203}\overline{\text{Tl}} \leftarrow {}_{80}^{201}\overline{\text{Hg}} + {}_1^2\overline{\text{D}}$
242. ${}_{81}^{203}\text{Tl} + {}_1^2\text{D} \rightarrow {}_{82}^{205}\text{Pb} + e \rightarrow {}_{81}^{205}\text{Tl} \leftrightarrow {}_{81}^{205}\overline{\text{Tl}} \leftarrow {}_{82}^{205}\overline{\text{Pb}} + \bar{e} \leftarrow {}_{81}^{203}\overline{\text{Tl}} + {}_1^2\overline{\text{D}}$
243. ${}_{79}^{197}\text{Au} + {}_3^7\text{Li} \rightarrow {}_{82}^{204}\text{Pb} \leftrightarrow {}_{82}^{204}\overline{\text{Pb}} \leftarrow {}_{79}^{197}\overline{\text{Au}} + {}_3^7\overline{\text{Li}}$
244. ${}_{80}^{202}\text{Hg} + {}_2^4\text{He} \rightarrow {}_{82}^{206}\text{Pb} \leftrightarrow {}_{82}^{206}\overline{\text{Pb}} \leftarrow {}_{80}^{202}\overline{\text{Hg}} + {}_2^4\overline{\text{He}}$
245. ${}_{80}^{204}\text{Hg} + {}_2^3\text{He} \rightarrow {}_{82}^{207}\text{Pb} \leftrightarrow {}_{82}^{207}\overline{\text{Pb}} \leftarrow {}_{80}^{204}\overline{\text{Hg}} + {}_2^3\overline{\text{He}}$
246. ${}_{80}^{204}\text{Hg} + {}_2^4\text{He} \rightarrow {}_{82}^{208}\text{Pb} \leftrightarrow {}_{82}^{208}\overline{\text{Pb}} \leftarrow {}_{80}^{204}\overline{\text{Hg}} + {}_2^4\overline{\text{He}}$

${}_{40}^{94}\text{Zr}$, ${}_{50}^{124}\text{Sn}$, ${}_{78}^{198}\text{Pt}$ are observationally stable elements cannot be produced by any of the three processes.

${}_{40}^{94}\text{Zr}$, ${}_{50}^{124}\text{Sn}$, ${}_{78}^{198}\text{Pt}$ are observationally stable elements cannot be produced by any of the three processes.